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Master's Thesis

Potential of a Hypothetical Multi-Purpose Reservoir in the Upper Catchment Area of the Alptal

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Summary

Multi-purpose reservoirs have recently been discussed as an adaptation measure to mitigate the effects of climate change. The management of multi-purpose reservoirs, however, is challenging as trade-offs between compromising water uses need to be accounted for. A lot of studies elaborated optimizing reservoir operation rules by applying meta-heuristic techniques, whereas non-algorithmic approaches are currently missing in the literature. In addition, the potential and management of small reservoirs are rarely addressed. Thus, this Master's thesis has developed a simple methodology for the assessment of the potential of small multi-purpose reservoirs in pre-alpine catchments and applied it to a hypothetical reservoir in the Alptal. The main objective consisted in the proposal of an optimal reservoir design and management strategies considering all potential purposes of the reservoir. These purposes include (i) improving streamflow conditions for brown trout populations in the Alp, (ii) snowmaking, (iii) artificial flood experiments for research related to the morphology and control of torrents, (iv) flood retention and (v) tourism.

The methodology implied the simulation of the reservoir as a component of the streamflow network of the catchment area. Reservoir filling and water release was simulated in the "Water Evaluation And Planning" system (abbr. WEAP) by using an area-based approach to downscale high resolution discharge data (years 2009-2019). A specific water demand was assumed for every purpose, allowing their integration into the model and thus the evaluation of benefits.

The results show a great potential of a small reservoir ($< 30'000 \text{ m}^3$) for snowmaking under current climate conditions, for the conduction of artificial flood experiments and for the augmentation of streamflow during low flow periods. With respect to the latter, the reservoir's potential is limited during long periods of low flow for all analyzed reservoir sizes ($< 100'000 \text{ m}^3$). Thus, an intermittent streamflow augmentation may be considered, although studies providing evidence for stress reduction in brown trout have yet to be undertaken.

Regarding management strategies, trade-offs were analyzed by comparing the benefits of each purpose in both a single-purpose and multi-purpose reservoir system. This analysis allowed the formulation of adequate prioritization rules of different purposes throughout the year. In general, intermittent water uses such as snowmaking and tourism are prioritized over the continuous purpose of streamflow augmentation for brown trout. Furthermore, adequate management allows negative effects of summer tourism on streamflow augmentation to be compensated.

Thus, this Master's thesis concludes that there is a striking potential of a multi-purpose use of small reservoirs in pre-alpine areas if adequate operation rules are applied.

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1. Introduction

In Switzerland, streamflow regimes are highly influenced by the occurrence of snow and glaciers due to the prevalence of alpine headwater catchments. Global warming causes these regimes to change throughout the 21st century. According to Frei et al. (2018), winter snowfall will decrease by 25% (RCP4.5 emission scenario) resp. 45% (RCP8.5 emission scenario) in most parts of the Alps by the end of the century. As a consequence, winter rainfall is projected to increase in catchments with seasonal snow cover, i.e. at elevations above 1500 m a.s.l. (Santos et al., 2018), resulting in higher discharge during winter months (CH2018, 2018). Increasing temperatures will not only cause a significant decrease in snow amounts, but also the snowmelt season is expected to shift towards earlier spring months. In Switzerland, snowmelt contributes to approx. 40% of total discharge (BAFU, 2012) and reaches a peak during the months of May and June (Weingartner & Aschwanden, 1992). This contribution is expected to be reduced to approx. 25% by 2085 and to peak earlier in the year (FOEN, 2012), provoking a decrease in summer discharge. Furthermore, total glacier volume is expected to shrink to 30% of the existing volume by 2100 under moderate warming conditions (FOEN, 2012; Zekollari et al., 2019). Although glacier melt accounts for only 2% of annual discharge (Blanc & Schädler, 2013), in August the contribution can be up to 40% for watersheds like the Rhône at the Swiss boarder (Huss, 2011). Consequently, the decrease in the natural water storage in snow and ice will reduce discharge in summer months significantly in the long term (FOEN, 2012).

The effects of changes in glacier and snow cover towards lower summer discharge are intensified by a change in rainfall patterns. According to current climate scenarios for Switzerland (CH2018, 2018), summer precipitation is estimated to decrease, whereas heatwaves will become more frequent, more intense and longer-lasting. As a result, water scarcity will be enhanced in future summer months. In addition, higher temperatures provoke a higher water demand, for example for irrigation. According to Brunner et al. (2019, p. 1033), water shortages during summer months are expected “mainly in the lowland region north of the Alps, and less in the Alps”. However, Brunner et al. (2019) only considered anthropogenic water demand without addressing potential impacts of water shortages on alpine ecosystems.

Buisson et al. (2008) studied the effect of climate change on stream fish assemblages, concluding that headwater species will experience a strong reduction in number of suitable sites. This phenomenon has already been observed for the brown trout (*Salmo trutta fario*), a species occurring in cold, oxygen-rich streams in Switzerland (Burkhardt-Holm et al., 2002). Michel et al. (2020) have shown a significant increase of stream temperatures in Switzerland over the past five decades, especially during summer with a median trend of more than 0.5 °C per decade.

According to Hari et al. (2006), warming trends in water temperature towards the end of the 20th century have caused an upward shift of the thermal habitat of brown trout, resulting in a habitat decrease if physical barriers inhibited upstream migration. Importantly, higher water temperatures in summer do not only result from higher air temperatures but are to a certain extent also correlated with low water flow (Michel et al., 2020; Young et al., 2010). Hence, higher water temperatures and more frequent and intense low flow periods (CH2018, 2018) may have a detrimental effect on alpine fish communities in the future.

As a consequence, climate change will increase the pressure on water as a resource, especially during summer months. In this context, the use of multi-purpose reservoirs has recently been discussed as a possible adaptation measure in Switzerland (Brunner et al., 2019; FOEN, 2014; Kellner & Weingartner, 2018; Thut et al., 2016). Alpine reservoirs can store water from precipitation and snowmelt during winter and spring months and release it in summer, thereby alleviating water shortages. Reservoirs can be used for various purposes such as irrigation, augmentation of low water levels to favour freshwater ecosystems, flood protection, water supply, fire protection, recreational activities and system services (Brunner et al., 2019; Kellner & Weingartner, 2018). However, the potential of multi-purpose reservoirs is not restricted to water release during summer months, as they can also provide water for hydropower production and snowmaking in winter. Moreover, the storage capacity of reservoirs can be used for flood protection by attenuating flood peaks or for sediment retention (Kellner & Weingartner, 2018; Sander, 2002). This service may gain in importance, as flood intensities are projected to increase in the future (CH2018, 2018). These examples illustrate the great potential of multi-purpose reservoirs, which may become increasingly important when effects of climate change will be stronger.

The management of multi-purpose reservoirs, however, is complex, since it needs to accommodate various and often conflicting purposes (Liu et al., 2011). This refers to the challenge of addressing trade-offs between different water uses in decision making processes. Moreover, streamflow remains difficult to forecast and thereby the urgency for water release from the reservoir (e.g. during low flow) as well as reservoir filling processes are difficult to project. Still, many different approaches and mathematical models for the elaboration of optimized operation rules for multi-purpose reservoirs have been part of academic discussions for several decades (e.g. Fults & Hancock, 1972; Mobasher & Harboe, 1970; Sigvaldson, 1976).

An optimal operation usually involves optimization and simulation models in order to obtain quantitative information for improving operational water management (Lin & Rutten, 2016). For the optimization model, different objectives (i.e. purposes) of the reservoir and constraints need to be identified, each of which is expressed in an objective function. Thus, operation is expressed in the model “as a set of linear or nonlinear formulas with one or more objective functions in order to achieve desired objectives” (Ahmadi et al., 2014, p. 132). Multi-objective optimization problems are usually solved using meta-heuristic techniques (e.g. evolutionary

algorithms and swarm intelligence techniques). They normally result in so-called Pareto-optimal solutions, representing the most efficient compromises/trade-offs (Malekmohammadi et al., 2011).

Although many optimal operation methods have been studied (cf. Ahmad et al., 2014; Jahandideh-Tehrani et al., 2020), no universally accepted technique for the operation of a reservoir system exists. As illustrated, most methods found in the literature include complex mathematical algorithms for the optimization of reservoir management, whereas approaches that do not imply specialized knowledge of complex formulas are barely available.

In this work, we want to propose a method for the assessment of the multi-purpose potential of reservoirs, including decisions about reservoir location and design, as well as the identification of potential purposes and appropriate reservoir operation rules. For the latter, we propose to use a heuristic approach that implies a reservoir simulation model. By heuristic we mean that we will analyze the effects of varying water allocation priorities on different purposes in the simulation model in order to identify appropriate reservoir operation rules. The advantage of this approach is that the effect of different management strategies can be compared directly within the simulation model instead of defining complex objective functions that are solved in an additional model. Consequently, the approach depends less on mathematical and numerical expertise. This facilitates its application especially to small reservoir projects with little financial resources, which is the scope of the here presented work.

As reservoir designs and their multi-purpose objectives vary greatly between different case studies, the application of concepts and methods is complicated. In the past, mainly large reservoirs (e.g. Liu et al., 2011; Malekmohammadi et al., 2011) or systems of multiple reservoirs (e.g. Li & Wei, 2008) have been studied. Many of the case studies investigate reservoirs in Asia (especially China) and deal with the objectives of hydropower production, flood protection and water supply during droughts (Heydari et al., 2015; Kumar & Reddy, 2006; Li & Wei, 2008; Wu & Chen, 2012).

The potential of small reservoirs, however, has largely been neglected in water resource management research. Andreini et al. (2009) argue that several characteristics such as small size, existence in large numbers, and widespread distribution make monitoring of small reservoirs difficult. Few studies have investigated the storage capacities and importance of small reservoirs for the livelihood of the rural population in semi-arid areas (e.g. Liebe et al., 2005; Sawunyama et al., 2006). This tendency is also valid for the Alps, where mainly the operation of hydropower reservoirs has been studied (e.g. Meile et al., 2009; Müller, 2014). The potential of small alpine reservoirs, however, considering multiple purposes except hydropower, has not been addressed in a case study so far.

The objective of this thesis is to propose a methodology to assess the potential of a small multi-purpose reservoir ($< 100'000 \text{ m}^3$) in the upper catchment area of the Alptal (Badoux et al., 2012; Fischer et al., 2015; Gottselig et al., 2017; López-Moreno & Stähli, 2008; Stähli et al., 2002; Turowski et al., 2009; Van Meerveld et al., 2018). The reservoir does not yet exist, therefore the selection of a suitable location and reservoir design are part of the thesis. The Alptal is chosen as study area because high resolution time series of both hydrological and meteorological variables are available, which facilitates modelling substantially. Furthermore, this data availability has converted the Alptal into a research site of international importance for studying processes like runoff generation and groundwater interaction, sediment transport, snow hydrology, water quality and runoff-driven nutrient export. Consequently, a reservoir may also benefit research since a large amount of water is available to be released upon request.

The overarching research question is how a small reservoir in a valley like the Alptal can optimally be designed such as to serve several purposes simultaneously. Specifically, two purposes are discussed in detail: increasing water availability for snowmaking and improving habitat conditions for brown trout. The latter tries to address the difficulties this headwater species faces in the area, which are likely to increase if extreme events become more frequent (CH2018, 2018). Accordingly, the following detail questions will be investigated:

- To what extent can a multi-purpose reservoir in the upper catchment area of the Alptal valley improve streamflow conditions for brown trout (*Salmo trutta fario*) in the Alp stream?
- What is the benefit of a multi-purpose reservoir with regard to snowmaking in the ski resort Brunni-Haggenegg under current and future climate conditions?
- How should the multi-purpose reservoir be designed and managed in order to limit trade-offs and thereby optimize the benefits of its potential uses?

Accordingly, the potential of the hypothetical reservoir is assessed in three steps. First, possible water uses within the catchment are identified. Considering these purposes, a suitable reservoir location and design is suggested (chapter 2). In a second step, the reservoir is modelled as a component of the streamflow network of the upper catchment area of the Alptal. A framework for each purpose is elaborated, which allows its incorporation into the model and thereby the evaluation of the benefits the reservoir may have for it (chapter 3). In a last step, management rules of the reservoir considering all its potential uses are elaborated heuristically by analyzing the effect of varying water allocation priorities (chapter 4 and 5).

Thus, this Master's thesis may serve as a first prototype of how small multi-purpose reservoirs (volumes $< 100'000 \text{ m}^3$) located in small pre-alpine catchments ($< 1 \text{ km}^2$) could be designed and managed by considering various uses and the associated trade-offs.

2. Case study: Catchment characteristics and reservoir

Hereafter, the study area is presented, including the hypothetical reservoir, designed based on the streamflow statistics of one subcatchment.

2.1 Alptal and relevant subcatchments

The study area includes the upper watershed of the Alptal, a south-north oriented, pre-alpine valley in central Switzerland. It is located south of Lake Zurich and is part of the Rhine river basin. The Alptal covers an area of 46.7 km² with an elevation range from 840-1898 m a.s.l. The valley has a topography with slopes of 20-40 degrees, the mean slope of the entire catchment is 15.2 degrees. Precipitation patterns show a distinct north-south gradient, with a long-term average of 1790 mm/year in Einsiedeln (880 m a.s.l.) and 2300 mm/year in Erlenbach (1220 m a.s.l.) (Ragetti et al., 2020, published online). A continuous snow cover of up to 2 m thickness is present from December to April in normal winters, although the snowpack may not last throughout the entire winter season due to regular rainfall at lower elevations (< 1300 m a.s.l.) (Stähli et al., n.d., in review).

Figure 1: Watershed of the Alptal with focus on the upper catchment area.

The predominant soil type of the Alptal is Gleysol on top of Flysch bedrock. Its low permeability results in shallow groundwater levels, thus causing a fast response of the catchment to rainfall events (Van Meerveld et al., 2018). Almost half of the catchment is covered by coniferous forest, mainly with Norway spruce (*Picea abies*) and silver fir (*Abies alba*) (Ragetti et al., 2020, published online).

The eponymous stream of the Alptal, the Alp, is supplied by various smaller streams, among these the Erlenbach, Lümpenenbach and Vogelbach. Located at each, a streamflow gauge has been in operation for more than 40 years. Next to the Erlenbach, at the Erlenhöhe (1220 m a.s.l.), a station recording various meteorological variables (air temperature, precipitation, relative humidity, wind speed, global radiation and snow depth) has been in place since 1968. Data is monitored by the Swiss Federal Institute of Forest, Snow and Landscape Research WSL. Characteristics of the three research catchments Erlenbach, Lümpenenbach and Vogelbach are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Characteristics of the three research catchments in the Alptal. Data from Gottselig et al. (2017) and WSL.

	Erlenbach	Lümpenenbach	Vogelbach
Area [km ²]	0.73	0.88	1.58
Average elevation [m a.s.l.]	1330	1260	1285
Average slope	0.24	0.15	0.23
Fraction of forest cover [%]	39	19	63
Fraction of saturated areas [%]	61	24	25
Annual precipitation [mm] ¹⁾	2306	2372	2106
Annual runoff [mm] ¹⁾	1636	2016	1514
Annual evapotranspiration [mm] ¹⁾	670	356	592

¹⁾ Mean 1988-2017

Most studies of the Alptal, especially those investigating sediment transport, have been conducted at the Erlenbach catchment due to the availability of a retention basin (built in 1982) and installed geophone sensors (Badoux et al., 2012). Thus, sediment loads can be measured and related to individual rainfall events. Several studies have investigated erosion processes during flood events, such as thresholds for bedload transport initiation (Badoux et al., 2012; Masteller et al., 2019), relationships between stream power and bedload volume (Schneider et al., 2014) and thresholds for bedrock erosion (Turowski et al., 2013). Studying these processes requires a high temporal resolution of data (e.g. Badoux et al., 2012), especially because the streams respond rapidly to precipitation (within minutes to an hour) (Fischer et al., 2017). As the prediction of flood events in alpine areas is challenging (cf. Liechti et al., 2013; Schaeffli et al., 2007; Sikorska & Seibert, 2018; Verbunt et al., 2007), recording of high resolution data is complicated. Therefore, the possibility of artificial flood experiments by releasing water from a reservoir would benefit future research, since measuring instruments could be installed prior to the event, providing high resolution data to be recorded during the event.

The Erlenbach catchment, however, is located within a cantonal nature reserve (Canton of Schwyz, 2020). Hence, the construction of a multi-purpose reservoir within the catchment would be very difficult. Other possible locations are within the Lümpenenbach or the Vogelbach catchment. As the Lümpenenbach is part of the ski resort Brunni-Haggenegg, a reservoir could benefit the resort through snowmaking. Due to this additional possibility of use, the hypothetical multi-purpose reservoir will be located within the Lümpenenbach catchment.

2.2 Hydrology of the Lümpenenbach

The reservoir design (cf. section 2.3) is based on the hydrological statistics of the Lümpenenbach catchment, which is discussed in the following. Figure 2 shows the monthly mean and median discharge values at the Lümpenenbach streamflow gauge (cf. Figure 1). Values are generally around 30 l/s. During the months of March, April and May, the median values range between 50 and 90 l/s, which can be explained by the snowmelt pattern in pre-alpine areas (Gustafsson et al., 2004; Keller et al., 2004). The mean values are lowest in autumn and winter, showing less than 30 l/s in the month of February. The deviation between the mean and median values is highest in the period from June to August. This can be explained by intensive precipitation events in summer which have a strong effect on daily streamflow values.

In fact, the Lümpenenbach shows a high dynamic in terms of daily streamflow variability as well as interannual streamflow variability (cf. Figure A 1 in Appendix A). The former can vary over three to four orders of magnitude, indicating a very rapid response of the catchment to rainfall events (Stähli et al., n.d., in review).

Figure 2: Median and mean discharge values per month of the Lümpenenbach for the period 1999-2019.

2.3 Reservoir design

Given the overall low water quantities, the hypothetical reservoir is not located on the stream but offline, i.e. decoupled from the stream channel. This independence of the reservoir has the following advantages:

- Reservoir filling can be restricted to days with high discharge. Hence, on days of low flow, the inflow channel can be closed, and the reservoir does not negatively affect the flow of the stream.
- Several purposes of the reservoir such as snowmaking only require water during specific months of the year. Thus, the reservoir does not require a continuous in- and outflow, which makes reservoir management simpler.
- If there is a flood event and no filling of the reservoir is necessary, the reservoir inflow channel can be closed in order to avoid deposition of sediments in the reservoir basin.
- Construction and possible maintenance processes are facilitated because no temporary diversions of the natural streambed need to be made.

Figure 3: Scheme of the reservoir. Drawing inspired by the Laboratory of Hydraulic Constructions of EPFL.

A scheme of the reservoir installation is depicted in Figure 3. Importantly, the dam on the stream is not an impermeable dam, but always leaves a minimum quantity of water Q_{min} to the downstream area. This fraction can be increased at higher discharges if no filling of the reservoir is required. Adjacent to the dam, there is an installation for water withdrawal, diverting a part of the streamflow into the reservoir's inflow channel. The reservoir itself has two openings for water outflow that can be shut completely if there is no water demand. One leads directly to a consumption site, e.g. snowmaking installations. Hence, the water return point is diffuse and delayed in time. The other opening is connected to an outflow channel releasing water directly into the original stream channel, thus enabling streamflow regulations.

An important parameter is the design volume of the reservoir V_d , representing the maximum amount of water that is available for storage in the reservoir. According to Hänggi and Weingartner (2012) it can be calculated from the flow duration curve (cf. Figure A 2 in Appendix A) by defining two flow parameters:

- The **design discharge** Q_d which represents the maximum water intake to the reservoir. The design discharge is a key value when designing hydropower plants and depends on the purpose of the plant (Hänggi & Weingartner, 2012). For the reservoir at the Lümpenenbach, Q_1 with a value of 672 l/s is chosen as design discharge, meaning that even the highest daily discharge within a year can be withdrawn to the reservoir. A high design discharge increases the capacity for flood retention, since a higher discharge fraction can be diverted from the stream channel to the reservoir, which reduces the risk of flooding downstream. Hence, choosing Q_1 as design discharge increases the reservoir's capacity for flood retention.
- The **minimum discharge** Q_{min} represents the water quantity that needs to be left in the stream for ecological reasons. According to the Swiss Water Protection Act, the minimum residual water quantity is determined by Q_{347} , i.e. the discharge that is met on 95% of the days per year (GSchG, 2020). For the Lümpenenbach, Q_{347} equals 7.9 l/s for the period 1999-2019. According to the Swiss Water Protection Act *art. 31*, no water abstraction is permitted if Q_{347} is lower than 50 l/s. However, there are several exceptions mentioned in *art. 32*. According to *art. 32 lit. b*, water withdrawal is allowed "from bodies of water not suitable as habitats for fish provided that the residual rate of flow represents at least 35 per cent of the flow rate Q_{347} " or *art. 32 lit. b^{bis}* "on a 1000 m long stretch below a place of withdrawal in sections with negligible ecological potential, provided the natural functions of the body of water are not substantially impaired" (GSchG, 2020). According to AquaPlus (2009), the Lümpenenbach is not a fishing water, whereas on the cantonal WebGIS platform (Canton of Schwyz, 2020) the lowest section is listed as fish habitat. Consequently, water abstraction from the Lümpenenbach may be possible, but the permission would rely on the approval of an eco-office, which would determine the residual water quantity Q_{min} . For simplicity, in this thesis Q_{min} is determined as 17.5 l/s (i.e. 35% of 50 l/s) following GSchG *art. 32 lit. b*.

Figure 4 shows the flow duration curve of the Lümpenenbach for the period 1999-2019. The period has been restricted to the past twenty years, since periods before 1999 show different values especially for high and low exceedance values (cf. Figure A 3 in Appendix A). The design volume V_d is defined by the formula of Hänggi and Weingartner (2012):

$$V_d = \sum_{i=t(Q_x)}^{t(Q_{min})} (Q_i - Q_{min}) * 3'600 * 24 \quad (1)$$

Consequently, the design volume V_d for the Lümpenenbach catchment equals:

$$V_d = 14.74 * 3600 * 24 = 1'273'536 \text{ m}^3$$

Hence, a reservoir located downstream of the Lümpenenbach streamflow gauge would have a daily inflow of 40 l/s on average. However, inflow may strongly vary due to the high dynamics of daily streamflow (cf. Figure A 1 in Appendix A). Importantly, the storage capacity (i.e. reservoir volume) is not specified previously. Instead, the benefits of the reservoir for several purposes are analyzed by using different volumes between 5'000 m³ and 100'000 m³, which is within the range of Swiss dams used for snowmaking (Iseli, 2015). As the reservoir volume is variable, no vertical zonation of the reservoir (upper and lower limits) and no volume-elevation curve are suggested.

Figure 4: Flow duration curve of the Lümpenenbach for the period 1999-2019. Q_d = design discharge, Q_{min} = minimum discharge, V_d = design volume, V_{rest} = volume not utilizable for the reservoir.

2.4 Reservoir location

In the following, two options for the location of a multi-purpose reservoir within the Lümpenenbach catchment are presented. The options consider hydrological and geomorphological aspects as well as legal limitations. The following criteria are decisive for the choice of the potential locations:

- Small inclination of the terrain
- Proximity to the Lümpenenbach
- Road access

2.4.1 Reservoir at Brüschrain

Considering the main criteria listed above, the terrain “Brüschrain” is ideal for the construction of a reservoir within the Lümpenenbach catchment. Directly south of the “Haggenegg” street, the terrain shows a terrace-like structure with a very low inclination (Figure 5 and Figure 6). Two channels of the Lümpenenbach are located south and north of the reservoir, thus providing two points for water withdrawal to fill the reservoir. Moreover, the street access to the reservoir is provided from the side of the Alptal valley.

Figure 5: Brüschrain location (south-west perspective).

Figure 6: Possible location of the hypothetical reservoir at Brüschrain within the Lümpenenbach catchment. Equidistance = 10 m.

The land belongs to the cooperative of the municipality of Schwyz. However, the area is classified as a fen of national importance, which may complicate the permission for an artificial reservoir. In addition, high groundwater levels cause swampy conditions, which may complicate the construction process and reservoir maintenance (Peyras et al., 2011).

2.4.2 Reservoir at Nätschberg base station

Due to the legal limitations of the Brüschrain terrain, an alternative location outside of the protected area is proposed. It is situated lower in the catchment area, northeast of the ski lift “Nätschberg” base station. The slope is steeper compared to Brüschrain (Figure 7 and Figure 8), which may increase construction costs for excavation. The plot belongs to a single farmer and is classified as agricultural zone without special biodiversity support constraints (Canton of Schwyz, 2020). Thus, the permission for the construction of a reservoir may be easier to obtain.

Figure 7: Nätschberg location (north-east perspective).

Figure 8: Possible location of the hypothetical reservoir at Nätschberg base station within the Lämpenerbach catchment. Equidistance = 10 m.

2.5 Reservoir uses

For the identification of potential uses of the reservoir, the applicability of multiple purposes of reservoirs mentioned by Jossen and Gurung (2018), Kellner and Weingartner (2018) and Brunner et al. (2019) is considered, which are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Multiple purposes of reservoirs. Categories according to Jossen and Gurung (2018).

Category	Purpose
Energetic function	Electricity generation (hydropower)
Protective function	Flood retention
	Sediment retention
	Modulation of streamflow regimes
Usage of water	Domestic water supply (drinking water)
	Irrigation
	Fire-fighting water
	Artificial snowmaking
Ecology	Coolant
	Provision of residual water quantities
Social function	Artificial floods
	Recreational activities/tourism
	Infrastructure of the reservoir (education)
	Fishery

According to informal conversations with local farmers, fires have not been an issue in the study area, neither have water shortages for alpine farming occurred in the past. Regarding electricity generation, the Lümpepenbach is unlikely to be profitable for hydropower since the catchment has a median discharge of 27 l/s (period 1999-2019) and shows only moderate differences in altitude. Thus, the proposed purposes of fire-fighting water, irrigation, domestic water supply and electricity generation are not investigated any further.

The remaining purposes are grouped into the following main uses a reservoir in the Lümpepenbach catchment could potentially have:

- Improvement of streamflow conditions for brown trout populations in the Alp stream
- Artificial snowmaking to complement snow shortages in the ski resort Brunnig-Haggenegg
- Artificial flood experiments for conducting research related to the morphology and control of torrents (long-term research topic of the Swiss Federal Research Institute WSL)
- Flood retention
- Recreational activities (e.g. hiking tourism)

The elaboration of the framework conditions for these purposes as well as their integration into the reservoir model are described in the sections 3.3 to 3.5.

3. Methods

3.1 Reservoir simulation model in WEAP

In order to assess the potential of a hypothetical reservoir in the Lümpenenbach catchment, the multi-purpose reservoir is simulated as a component of the streamflow network of the catchment areas of the Lümpenenbach and the Alp (until the village of Alpthal). The simulation model is designed in the “Water Evaluation And Planning” (abbr. WEAP) software, developed by the Stockholm Environment Institute (Yates et al., 2005). WEAP has been used in various research projects in the field of water resource management (Agarwal et al., 2018; Duque & Vázquez, 2017; Metobwa et al., 2018; Tsoukalas & Makropoulos, 2015). WEAP allows the specification of various water supplies (rivers, groundwater, other catchments, reservoirs) and water demands and their interconnection to simulate a complete water management system by incorporating meteorological and/or hydrological datasets. The maximum temporal resolution is daily values.

In this thesis, WEAP is used to simulate reservoir filling and to evaluate the benefit of water release from the reservoir for various water uses. The model does not rely on meteorological variables but on streamflow measurements. Long time series of the Lümpenenbach streamflow gauge (10min resolution) and of the BAFU station in Einsiedeln (1h resolution) are used. The main advantage of using streamflow data is that soil infiltration processes, groundwater response and the effect of snowmelt are already included in the data. Hence, the relationship between precipitation and streamflow generation does not need to be modelled.

For the model set-up, the identification of water demands and the determination of water supply within the system is crucial. The latter follows an area-based approach and is explained in section 3.2. The identification of water demands for the purposes mentioned in section 2.5 is described in the sections 3.3 to 3.5.

In the following, the structure of the model is explained. A schematic view of the model is shown in Figure 9. In total, three rivers are defined: “Lümpenenbach”, “Alp” and “Inflow between Brunni and Alpthal”. The latter is not a real river but represents the totality of all tributaries of the Alp between the villages Brunni and Alpthal. The Lümpenenbach is the other tributary in the model. Other tributaries of the Alp which are located upstream of the inflow point of the Lümpenenbach (e.g. Erlenbach) are summarized as “headflow” of the Alp. For every stream section, in WEAP called “reaches”, a surface water inflow is defined. Thus, the total discharge of a reach consists of the accumulated inflow of upstream reaches and the surface water inflow of the respective reach. The determination of surface water inflow is discussed in section 3.2. As the scheme suggests, the analysis of the effect of the reservoir on the streamflow

of the Alp is restricted to the section between Brunni and Alpthal. This choice is based on the consideration that the effect of the reservoir on the streamflow of the Alp is most pronounced in the section directly downstream of the Lümpenenbach inflow point.

Figure 9: Scheme of the reservoir system model in WEAP. Numbers in brackets display the priority of the respective element. AFE = Artificial Flood Experiments.

As described in section 2.3, the reservoir is located off-stream of the Lümpenenbach. WEAP provides several parameters for defining reservoir characteristics. The storage capacity (i.e. reservoir volume) is not defined in advance. Instead, the benefit of the reservoir for the different purposes mentioned in section 2.5 is evaluated for various storage capacities between 5'000 m³ and 100'000 m³. Thus, an adequate reservoir size can be approximated. Additional parameters in WEAP include different zones of the reservoir (cf. Figure A 4 in Appendix A). For simplicity, these parameters are not defined. Thus, the entire reservoir volume is available for water allocation with no restrictions (except for the purpose of tourism, cf. section 3.5.3). This is not realistic in terms of reservoir construction, but serves the purpose since the reservoir is hypothetical, meaning only the active storage is of interest. Therefore, in case of a construction of the reservoir, the reservoir volumes that are suggested within this thesis would need to be completed by an inactive zone and flood control zone volume.

Reservoir filling and water release from the reservoir are achieved via an inflow and outflow channel, defined as “transmission links” in WEAP. The reservoir has an additional transmission link to the demand site of snowmaking. Figure 9 shows a total of five flow requirements.

They serve to define a minimum discharge for certain points within the river network. The purposes of these flow requirements are described in the sections 3.2.3, 3.3.1, 3.3.2 and 3.5.1.

In Figure 9, each flow requirement and demand site is followed by a number in brackets. This number represents the demand priority; the highest demand priority being 1. Demand priorities are used to determine the order of water allocation. This means, if on a day there are two demands (e.g. a flow requirement and a demand site) connected to the same source of water, water resources are allocated to the demand of higher priority. If two demands show the same priority, WEAP follows a simultaneous water allocation (SEI, 2020). Importantly, the flow requirement “Residual Water” is assigned the highest priority (1), followed by the different purposes of the reservoir (priority 2).

In WEAP, a model can encompass different scenarios. Scenarios are used to analyze the effect of different model assumptions on the results without changing the overall structure of the model. The status quo scenario, which tries to reflect the present hydro system without changes in the future, is called “reference scenario”. Since the reservoir is hypothetical, in the reference scenario the reservoir and the corresponding transmission links are inactive. In section 2.4, two different reservoir locations are proposed. Therefore, two scenarios named “Brüschrain” and “Nätschberg” are created to account for hydrological differences in reservoir location (cf. section 3.2.3). In both scenarios, the reservoir and the transmission links are active.

3.2 Simulation of water availability and validation

The definition of water availability at different reaches of the model is crucial for the simulation of reservoir inflow and the determination of flow requirements. Water availability is simulated following an area-based approach by using streamflow data of the Lümpenenbach streamflow gauge (10min resolution) and of the BAFU station of the Alp in Einsiedeln (1h resolution). The approach, its validation and integration into the model are explained in the following sections.

3.2.1 Area-based approach for streamflow simulation

The area-based approach suggests water amounts within subcatchments to increase linearly with catchment size. For the Lümpenenbach, it is important to know the water availability at the reservoir inflow channels of the two selected reservoir locations (cf. section 2.4) in order to simulate reservoir inflow. Therefore, the subcatchments of the reservoir locations “Brüschrain” and “Nätschberg” are calculated in ArcGIS using the digital elevation model “swissALTI3D” from swisstopo (resolution 5x5 m, year 2011). The computation follows the manual for watershed delineation published by the Trent University (MaDGIC, 2014). Then, the percentage share of each subcatchment within the entire Lümpenenbach catchment is calculated. Following the area-based approach, the resulting factor can be used to downscale the streamflow data recorded at the Lümpenenbach station in order to obtain the streamflow at the reservoir inflow channel. As an example, if the subcatchment of a reservoir is 50% of the entire Lümpenenbach

catchment, the water availability is assumed to be 50% of the discharge measured at the Lämpenenbach streamflow gauge.

The streamflow of the Alp is modelled with the same approach but by downscaling streamflow data from the BAFU station in Einsiedeln. Two flow requirements are defined within the Alp: one is located in Brunni (downstream of the Lämpenenbach inflow point), the other in the village Alphal (cf. Figure 9 in section 3.1). Thus, streamflow values need to be modelled for these two points in order to know on which days the streamflow is below the flow requirements. Hence, the subcatchments in Brunni (downstream of the Lämpenenbach inflow point) and Alphal, and their percentage shares in the catchment area of Einsiedeln are calculated. Eventually, the discharge at the two flow requirements is calculated by downscaling the streamflow data of Einsiedeln according to the respective percentage shares.

3.2.2 Approach validation

The area-based approach is a key assumption since it defines the streamflow in the Lämpenenbach and Alp as well as the water amounts disposable for reservoir filling. The latter directly influences the potential of the reservoir for multiple purposes. Therefore, the approach is validated with salt tracer experiments conducted on three days in summer 2020. Discharge was measured in the Lämpenenbach at the hypothetical inflow channels in Brüschrain and Nätschberg, and at the Lämpenenbach streamflow gauge in order to ensure the comparability of the measurements. In the Alp, streamflow was measured in Brunni downstream of the Lämpenenbach inflow point and in the village Alphal south of the communal church (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Selected sites (pink dots) for the conduction of the field measurements. s.g. = streamflow gauge.

Field measurements were conducted on the 22.07.2020, 17.08.2020 and 29.08.2020. On the first two dates, cumulative 24h precipitation was below 10 mm (cf. Figure A 8 in Appendix B) and discharge volumes were low compared to monthly mean values (cf. Table 3). Hence, the measurements are representative for summer baseflow. On the 29.08.2020, cumulative 24h precipitation was almost 30 mm and discharge was remarkably higher. Moreover, precipitation was more intense towards the evening and differences in discharge at the same spots between different hours were visible (cf. Figure A 10 in Appendix B). Thus, streamflow on the 29.08.2020 may represent the beginning of high flow conditions, especially since discharge increased further after the measurements (cf. Figure A 9 in Appendix B).

For the salt tracer measurements, *SOMMER* probes were used on the 22.07.2020 and *WTW 3420* probes on the 17.08.2020 and 29.08.2020. In the Lümpepenbach, two probes were used for each measurement. In the Alp, the channel is several meters wide, therefore narrow spots along the channel were selected for the measurements. A total of three probes were distributed along the cross-section in order to cover the variability of the discharge. The calibration coefficients of the probes were determined for water of the Lümpepenbach and for water of the Alp in the laboratory after the measurements. For each measurement, the resulting discharge represents the mean of all probes involved.

For the validation, the ratios of the discharge measured at the hypothetical inflow channels (of Brüschrain resp. Nätschberg) to the discharge measured at the Lümpepenbach streamflow gauge are calculated. Importantly, the latter refers to the discharge measured using salt tracer experiments and not to the recorded values of the Lümpepenbach station. The recorded values at the streamflow gauge, however, are used for time correction to account for the effect of discharge evolution. Hence, the measured discharge values are scaled according to relative differences (%) in streamflow recorded at the streamflow gauge (throughout the time horizon of the measurements).

Table 3: Validation of the area-based approach for the Lümpepenbach. Green: Area-based ratios of the subcatchments. Blue: Discharge ratios based on field measurements.

Lümpepenbach	Area [km ²]	% Lümpepen- bach	Q [l/s] 22.07.2020 12:10	% Lümpepen- bach	Q [l/s] 17.08.2020 11:30	% Lümpepen- bach	Q [l/s] 29.08.2020 12:10	% Lümpepen- bach
Brüschrain (total)	0.197	22.3	14.2	52.9	13.4	47.2	16.4	23.6
Nätschberg	0.572	64.5	22.8	85.1	23.1	81.5	57.1	82.1
Streamflow gauge	0.886	100.0	26.8	100.0	28.4	100.0	69.6	100.0

Table 3 depicts the resulting ratios from the field measurements and the ratios following the area-based approach mentioned in section 3.2.1. During low flow conditions (22.07.2020 and 17.08.2020), the area-based approach underestimates the water quantity of the Lümpepenbach at Brüschrain by more than 20%. On the 29.08.2020, the ratio of the field measurement shows a difference of less than 2% to the area-based ratio. At Nätschberg, the area-based approach underestimates the streamflow of all field measurements by more than 15%.

In the Alp, the ratios of the discharge measured in Brunni resp. Alpthal to the discharge recorded in Einsiedeln are calculated. Since no tracer experiments were conducted in Einsiedeln, the recorded streamflow values of the BAFU station are used. In addition, the recorded values are used for time correction (same as above). The resulting ratios are listed in Table 4. In Brunni, the area-based approach underestimates discharge by less than 15% on the 17.08.2020 and 29.08.2020. In Alpthal, the differences between the area-based ratio and ratios of the discharge measurements are less than 10% for all three field measurements.

Table 4: Validation of the area-based approach for the Alp. Green: Area-based ratios of the subcatchments. Blue: Discharge ratios based on field measurements. NA = Not Available.

Alp	Area [km ²]	% Einsiedeln	Q [l/s]	% Einsiedeln	Q [l/s]	% Einsiedeln	Q [l/s]	% Einsiedeln
			22.07.2020 15:00		17.08.2020 14:00		29.08.2020 11:00	
Brunni	9.0	19.3	NA	NA	122	20.3	334	30.7
Alpthal	16.1	34.5	308	38.9	244	40.5	352	32.4
Einsiedeln*	46.7	100.0	791	100.0	603	100.0	1087	100.0

*Source: BAFU

3.2.3 Approach integration in the reservoir model

Table 3 shows that the area-based approach tends to underestimate the streamflow at the Brüschrain location during low flow conditions. Similarly, at Nätschberg streamflow values are more than 15% higher during all field experiments than predicted by the area-based approach. Therefore, the area-based ratios of the Lümpenenbach are adjusted for the integration into the model: We assume water amounts to be **40%** at Brüschrain resp. **80%** at Nätschberg of the discharge measured at the Lümpenenbach streamflow gauge.

Importantly, not the entire streamflow at the reservoir inflow channel can be withdrawn to the reservoir, since residual water quantities need to be respected. Therefore, the flow requirement “Residual Water” is located downstream of the reservoir inflow channel in the Lümpenenbach (cf. Figure 9). The flow requirement is assigned the highest priority, thus ensuring that the flow requirement is always met before withdrawing water to the reservoir. The residual water quantity at the Lümpenenbach streamflow gauge is determined as 17.5 l/s (cf. section 2.3). Hence, the residual water quantity at the reservoir inflow channel is calculated by downscaling this quantity using the adjusted ratios of the Brüschrain and Nätschberg subcatchments. Consequently, the “Residual Water” flow requirement is set to 7 l/s (Brüschrain scenario) resp. 14 l/s (Nätschberg scenario).

For the Alp, the area-based approach underestimates discharge by less than 15% according to the field measurements. Therefore, the area-based approach is implemented without adjustment for the Alp in the model. The downscaled streamflow of Brunni and Alpthal (cf. section 3.2.1) are incorporated as follows. It is necessary to simulate the streamflow in the Alp without the discharge fraction from the Lümpenenbach, since in the reservoir scenarios the discharge of the Lümpenenbach is altered by reservoir filling and water release processes. Thus, the streamflow recorded at the Lümpenenbach station is subtracted from both the streamflow in Brunni and the streamflow in Alpthal. The resulting streamflow of Brunni (i.e. without Lümpenenbach contribution) is defined as the headflow of the Alp in the model (cf. Figure 9). Another headflow to be determined is the headflow of the fictitious river “Inflow between Alpthal and Brunni”, representing all tributaries of the Alp between Brunni and Alpthal. It is determined by subtracting the streamflow in Brunni from the streamflow in Alpthal.

3.3 Improvement of streamflow conditions for brown trout (*Salmo trutta fario*)

Regarding stream ecology, it is investigated how a reservoir within the Lümpenenbach catchment could benefit brown trout populations in the Alp. The brown trout *Salmo trutta fario* is the only fish sighted in large numbers in the Alp stream (cf. Table A 4 in Appendix A). It is a predatory fish living in cold (average temperatures < 20 °C in summer), fast flowing and oxygen-rich waters. Furthermore, they require clean water with pH values close to neutral as well as riverbeds with coarse gravel or pebbles for reproduction (Baglinière & Maise, 1999). More information on the life cycle of *Salmo trutta fario* and its environmental constraints is provided in Appendix C.

According to Buisson et al. (2010), climate change is likely to increase temperature induced stress in coldwater species, therefore brown trout populations are expected to decrease. In fact, Friedl (1999) reported a decline in brown trout catch of about 50% in many Swiss rivers since the 1980s. According to Elliott (1981), the optimum temperature ranges between 4 and 19 °C, meaning that temperatures below and above this range induce stress. In the Alp, water temperatures at the BAFU station in Einsiedeln are rarely above 20 °C, while the highest daily water temperature recorded in the Erlenbach, Lümpenenbach and Vogelbach (i.e. tributaries of the Alp) is 19.5 °C in summer 2015. According to these measurements, brown trout populations in the upper section of the Alp were not likely to experience temperature induced stress in the past.

Still, the fishery supervisor of the district of Einsiedeln (J.K. personal communication 14.03.2020) states that water quantity has been a serious problem during past summer droughts. If water levels are low, conditions for brown trout individuals can become critical because migration is limited, and fishes can get trapped in water pools with increased temperature. Furthermore, warm water temperatures favour algae growth, which may lower the oxygen content in the water and tend to restrict fish movement (Jonsson & Jonsson, 2009). For brown trout migration a water depth of at least 20 cm is required (Crisp, 2000; Dönni et al., 2016). Moreover, no sills or obstacles higher than 80 cm should be present, otherwise fish ladders are needed. Some of the sills in the Alp between Brunni and Alpthal are higher than 70 cm (Canton of Schwyz, 2020). Thus, during low flow they are likely to limit fish movement. Importantly, low water levels are not only problematic in summer but also during spawning season in autumn and winter, when eggs are laid in gravel beds (J.K. personal communication 14.03.2020). Since preferred spawning sites are in rather shallow areas (Jonsson & Jonsson, 2011), eggs can dry out during long-lasting low flow periods. Therefore, a purpose of the reservoir is to augment critical low water levels in the Alp and thereby improve living conditions for brown trout populations. The determination of a critical low water level is discussed in the following section.

3.3.1 Determination of a minimum flow requirement (MFR)

The effect of intentional water release of the reservoir on the discharge of the Alp is analyzed for the section between the Alp in Brunni and the village Alpthal (Figure 11). The determination of a critical low water level and associated streamflow in the Alp is crucial for the evaluation of this potential. In practice, there are various methods for the determination of a minimum discharge which take fish migration into account (cf. Appendix D). Since the environmental constraints of the brown trout concerning water temperature, water depth and water velocity have been extensively studied (Crisp, 1996; Heggenes, 1996; Jonsson & Jonsson, 2011) (cf. Appendix C), these methods could be applied. However, most methods rely on extensive field measurements of cross-sections and longitudinal profiles. For the section of the Alp between Brunni and Alpthal, however, no data of water levels or streamflow is available. Within the scope of this thesis, these methods are too time-consuming, considering that the main focus lies on the multi-purpose use of the reservoir and not on the optimization of a single use. Similarly, no hydraulic modelling of the riverbed is feasible (cf. Appendix D).

Figure 11: Relevant section (red) for the augmentation of low streamflow.

Therefore, we choose a more pragmatic approach for the determination of a minimum streamflow. A method suggested by the agency for environmental protection of Baden-Württemberg LfU (2005) considers a fraction of MNQ to be suitable to avoid potential damage to fish populations. MNQ is the arithmetic mean of the lowest daily discharge values of every year over a certain period of time. The role of the reservoir, however, should consist in actively improving the streamflow conditions for brown trout by ensuring higher water levels during periods of low flow. Therefore, the minimum discharge must be higher than MNQ .

In order to have an approximation for a reasonable minimum flow threshold, the values for $MN3Q$ resp. $MN7Q$ are computed on a seasonal basis for the BAFU station in Einsiedeln (period 1992-2018). They represent the lowest mean discharge values of 3 (resp. 7) consecutive days within a season. The $MNxQ$ values of all seasons except spring are considered, since low flow is less frequent in spring because of snowmelt in the study area (Gustafsson et al., 2004; Keller et al., 2004). Thus, brown trout are less expected to experience stress. Eventually, the $MN3Q$ and $MN7Q$ values are downscaled area-based to the $MNxQ$ of Brunni and Alpthal (using the factors 0.193 for Brunni and 0.345 for Alpthal, cf. Table 4 and section 3.2.1).

Another approach is based on the idea of Q_{347} , which is the minimum residual water quantity determined by the Swiss Water Protection Act (cf. section 2.3). Q_{347} is the discharge that is reached on 95% of the days per year. However, it might be too low to actively favour brown trout populations. Hence, the values of Q_{329} (i.e. the discharge reached on 90% of the days per year) and Q_{310} (85% of the days per year) are calculated using the streamflow data from Einsiedeln (period 1992-2018) and downscaling them area-based. The resulting values are listed in Table 5. For further statistical values of Q_{329} resp. Q_{310} and $MN3Q$ resp. $MN7Q$ consult Table A 1 to A 3 in Appendix A.

Table 5: Discharge mean values (unit = l/s) for the approximation of a minimum flow requirement. Values calculated for the period 1992-2018.

	Q_{329}	Q_{310}	MN7Q summer	MN7Q autumn	MN7Q winter	MN3Q summer	MN3Q autumn	MN3Q winter
Alp in Brunni	93	107	100	85	89	84	76	83
Alp in Alpthal	167	191	179	152	159	150	136	148
Alp in Einsiedeln	484	554	518	440	461	436	395	428

Values are between 80 l/s and 110 l/s in Brunni and 130 and 200 l/s in Alpthal. It is assumed that a reasonable minimum flow requirement (abbr. MFR) should be within this range. Thus, the potential of the reservoir to augment critical low flow is tested for two MFR combinations:

- 90 l/s in Brunni and 150 l/s in Alpthal
- 110 l/s in Brunni and 200 l/s in Alpthal

In the model (cf. Figure 9), these MFR combinations are implied by setting the flow requirement “Minimum Flow Brunni” to 90 l/s resp. 110 l/s and “Minimum Flow Alpthal” to 150 l/s resp. 200 l/s. It will be analyzed on how many days streamflow can be kept above these thresholds by comparing the reference with the Brüschrain and Nätschberg scenario.

3.3.2 Critical flood intensities

In the Alp, brown trout spawn during the months of October to December, whereas the incubation period lasts until end of March (AquaPlus, 2009). According to the fishery supervisor of the district (J.K. personal communication 14.03.2020), winter floods are problematic for brown trout because their eggs are deposited in gravel in the riverbed. Intense precipitation can pose a serious threat because the eggs may be destroyed during high flow events involving bedload transport. In the literature, this phenomenon has already been discussed within the context of climate change (Junker et al., 2015; Wenger et al., 2011), as flood events are projected to increase in winter (CH2018, 2018). Therefore, the reservoir could benefit brown trout populations by attenuating the peak of critical floods.

For the determination of the critical flood intensity, i.e. a flood intensity that involves bedload transport in the Alp, the formula of Bathurst (2013) is used:

$$q_c = 0.13 * g^{0.5} * D_{50}^{1.5} * S^{-1.146} \quad (2)$$

where:

q_c = Streamflow at which bedload transport begins (per meter channel width)

g = 9.81 m/s² (acceleration of gravity)

D_{50} = Characteristic grain size (m) of the riverbed for which 50% of the material is coarser

S = Mean slope gradient of the riverbed (m/m)

According to Rickenmann (1997), D_{50} of the Erlenbach ranges between 2-4 cm. Since the Erlenbach is a tributary of the Alp, a value of 3 cm is chosen as D_{50} . The slope is calculated using the digital elevation model “swissALTI3D” from swisstopo (resolution 5x5 m, year 2011). A total of 48 sills are installed between Brunni and Alpthal (Canton of Schwyz, 2020), which are considered in the slope calculation by subtracting an average sill height of 50 cm. The resulting mean slope gradient is 0.0213 m/m. The average width channel is assumed to be 8 m in Brunni and 12 m in Alpthal based on measurements conducted on sills within the respective section (cf. Figure A 6 and A 7 in Appendix B). Following formula (2), the critical flood intensity is 1.39 m³/s in Brunni and 2.09 m³/s in Alpthal.

In the model, the purpose of flood retention for brown trout is integrated as follows. The area-based contribution of the Lümpepenbach catchment to the catchment of the Alp in Brunni is only 10% (and 6% to the catchment of the Alp in Alpthal). Therefore, anytime the critical flood intensity would be reached in Brunni or Alpthal, the entire discharge fraction of the Lümpepenbach is withdrawn to the reservoir (except for the residual water quantity defined in section 3.2.3). Importantly, at the beginning of a critical flood event the reservoir needs to be empty. In WEAP, this is achieved with the flow requirement “Flood Retention Brown Trout” of the Lümpepenbach (cf. Figure 9). This flow requirement is always activated three days prior to a critical flood event during the period October 15th to March 31st (i.e. during the spawning and incubation season of brown trout in the Alp). The flow requirement is set to 500 l/s, which allows a reservoir of any size (< 100'000 m³) to be emptied in three days if natural streamflow of the Lümpepenbach does not exceed 100 l/s.

For the analysis, it is evaluated on how many days in the period 2009-2019 the reservoir can attenuate flood peaks sufficiently in order to inhibit the critical flood intensity to be reached in Brunni and/or Alpthal by comparing the reference to the Brüschrain and Nätschberg scenarios. Furthermore, the retained water volumes from the Lümpepenbach during successful flood attenuation events (i.e. streamflow remains below 1.39 m³/s in Brunni and 2.09 m³/s in Alpthal) are summed up over 1, 3 and 7 consecutive days. The maximum values display the necessary reservoir size to exploit the full retention potential of the reservoir.

3.4 Water demand for snowmaking

The catchment area of the Lümpenenbach is part of the ski resort Brunni-Haggenegg, which consists of two lifts shown in Figure 12 (Skilifte Brunni-Haggenegg AG, 2018). The three slopes of the lower T-bar lift are already groomed with technical snow by pumping water from the Fischerebach, a tributary of the Alp next to the Lümpenenbach. In contrast, the upper T-bar lift completely depends on the availability of natural snow. However, an extension of the snowmaking installation is unlikely, because the upper ski slopes are within a protection area classified as a fen of national importance (Skilifte Brunni-Haggenegg AG, 2014). Still, a reservoir can benefit the ski resort since it can replace water abstraction from the Fischerebach, which is limited. It enables water storing and thus a temporal decoupling of water abstraction and snowmaking.

Figure 12: Ski slopes of the ski resort "Brunni-Haggenegg" (based on the official map) including the length and area of the ski slopes (average width = 20 m) provided with technical snow (red).

Since Christmas holidays account for a large part of annual revenue of the ski resort (Skilifte Brunni-Haggenegg AG, 2018), it is important to take advantage of snowmaking for ski slope preparation in November and December. A robust ski slope consists of 40 cm of compact snow with a desired density of approx. 400 kg/m³ (Wolfspurger et al., 2018). This is equivalent to 160 cm depth of fresh snow (density 100 kg/m³), while snow density increases with snow age and water content (Wolfspurger et al., 2018). Thus, the required snow volume for slope preparation is calculated by multiplying the area of all ski slopes at Brunni-Haggenegg (average width of 20 m, cf. Figure 12) with 40 cm of snow depth (density 400 kg/m³).

For the analysis, the following questions are relevant:

- 1) How much snow can be produced in the ski resort Brunni-Haggenegg before Christmas holidays according to contemporary and future meteorological conditions? How many of the three slopes at Brunni-Haggenegg can be prepared with technical snow before Christmas using the hypothetical reservoir?
- 2) How much snow is appropriate to produce before Christmas holidays and how much water needs to remain in the reservoir for snowmaking during the following winter months?

The answers to these questions will allow us to propose an adequate reservoir size for snowmaking. The first questions imply the calculation of the technical snowmaking capacity, which is explained in section 3.4.1. The simulation of the natural snow cover is necessary to determine the demand for snowmaking and is described in section 3.4.2. Finally, both snowmaking capacity and natural snow cover data are used to define a daily water demand in the model to evaluate the potential of the reservoir for snowmaking. This is explained in section 3.4.3.

3.4.1 Technical snowmaking capacity

The technical snowmaking capacity describes the maximum snow volume that can be produced according to the meteorological conditions. In the following, the calculation of the snowmaking capacity of contemporary meteorological conditions (winters from 2005 to 2019) is explained. An overview of the workflow is illustrated in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Overview of the workflow to calculate the technical snowmaking capacity. Yellow: Field measurements. Blue: Information from the ski resort Brunni-Haggenegg. Green: Output data. Red arrows indicate conditions.

The production of technical snow depends mainly on two meteorological variables: air temperature and relative humidity. Both variables are required for the calculation of the wet-bulb temperature. Wet-bulb temperatures between $-2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $-4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ are referred to as the upper temperature limit for snowmaking (Wolfsperger et al., 2018). It is defined as the “lowest temperature to which air can be cooled by the evaporation of water into the air at a constant pressure” (Razak, 2007, p. 395). Consequently, the wet-bulb temperature is equal to the air temperature at a relative humidity of 100%.

For the determination of the snowmaking capacity, wet-bulb temperatures (T_w) are calculated on an hourly basis with the formula of Stull (2011) by using air temperature (T) and relative humidity (RH) data recorded at the Erlenbach station:

$$T_w = T * \operatorname{atan}\left(a * (RH + b)^{\frac{1}{2}}\right) + \operatorname{atan}(T + RH) - \operatorname{atan}(RH - c) + d * RH^{\frac{3}{2}} * \operatorname{atan}(e * RH) - f \quad (3)$$

where:

RH = Relative humidity in %	c = 1.676331
T = Temperature in °C	d = 0.00391838
a = 0.151977	e = 0.023101
b = 8.313659	f = 4.686035

The wet-bulb temperature is not only a precondition for snowmaking but also influences the snow-water ratio (SWR), i.e. how much water is used to produce a certain amount of snow. In comparison to fresh snow, the density of technically produced snow is higher and ranges between 350 and 550 kg/m³. Hence, technical snow does not need to be compressed when grooming the ski slope, meaning there is no direct volume loss. Theoretically, 1 m³ water could give a snow volume of 2.5 m³ (with a snow density of 400 kg/m³). However, in reality there are losses between 10 and 50 percent due to wind and evaporation, sublimation and melting processes (Wolfspurger et al., 2018). At a loss rate of 20%, out of 1 m³ water a snow volume of 2 m³ can be produced (SWR = 2), which could cover 5 m² of a ski slope (snow depth of 40 cm). In this thesis, a constant snow-water-ratio of 2 is assumed for snowmaking.

Moreover, the wet-bulb temperature has an effect on the efficiency of snow guns. Although wet-bulb temperatures between -2 °C and -4 °C already allow snowmaking, the efficiency increases with lower wet-bulb temperatures. This relationship is represented by the energy-snow-ratio (ESR) of different types of snow guns. In Brunni-Haggenegg two types are used: fan guns and snow lances. Following the ESR and productivity values listed in Wolfspurger et al. (2018, p. 54,56), the relationship between wet-bulb temperature and snow productivity of the snow guns translates to the values depicted in Figure 14. At wet-bulb temperatures between -3 °C and -10 °C the productivity of snow guns increases considerably: Both fan guns and snow lances produce about 3.6 m³ snow per hour at wet-bulb temperatures of -3 °C, whereas fan guns produce 85 m³/h and snow lances 44 m³/h at wet-bulb temperatures around -10 °C.

This difference in productivity is taken into account as follows: The number of hours per day with wet-bulb temperatures (WBT) below -3 °C is determined and the average WBT of these hours is calculated. This average WBT is used to calculate the daily snowmaking capacity (m³/h) at Brunni-Haggenegg by using the values depicted in Figure 14. The capacity is calculated for a snow gun inventory of 6 fan guns and 7 snow lances. Since snowmaking is less beneficial if snow guns only run for 1 or 2 hours (because turning the machines on and off takes

time), it is assumed that snowmaking is only profitable if WBT are below $-3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for at least 5 hours per day. Otherwise, the daily snowmaking capacity is zero.

Figure 14: Snow gun productivity of two types of snow guns. Data from Wolfsperger et al. (2018).

The snowmaking capacity for future climate scenarios is calculated similarly. For the analysis, EURO-CORDEX data from EUR-11 simulations (resolution $\sim 12.5 \times 12.5$ km) for Einsiedeln are used. The CORDEX initiative generates regional climate change projections for all terrestrial regions of the globe. The regional climate models (RCMs) of CORDEX are nested in the output of global climate models (GCMs) (CORDEX, 2020). For the analysis, the following simulation datasets are used:

- SMHI-RCA4-EC-EARTH: This simulation is generated by the Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI) using the GCM “EC-Earth” and the RCM “RCA4”.
- DMI-HIRHAM-ECEARTH: This simulation is generated by the Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI) using the GCM “EC-Earth” and the RCM “HIRHAM”.

The emission scenario RCP8.5 is used for the projection of both simulations. This scenario stands for unabated emissions and unmitigated warming (CH2018, 2018).

The Lümpenenbach catchment is located at a higher altitude (streamflow gauge at 1100 m a.s.l.) than Einsiedeln (880 m a.s.l.). Therefore, the temperature and air humidity data of the SMHI and DMI simulations are not directly applied but translated to the meteorological conditions of the Lümpenenbach catchment as follows. A simulation of daily air temperature (variable tas) and relative air humidity (variable hurs) from the SMHI resp. DMI dataset for Einsiedeln is selected. The monthly mean values of the period 1981-2010 (reference) and of the period 2021-2050 (future) are calculated and the delta is determined for each month

(future period – reference period). This delta reflects the mean change between the reference and future period for every month of the year.

In order to have an impression about the variability of change, the monthly mean values of the year 1981 are subtracted from the monthly mean values of the year 2021 and so forth (2022-1982 until 2050-2010). The resulting monthly deltas are tested for a normal distribution using the Shapiro-Wilk-Test in R. The null hypothesis cannot be rejected for the deltas of any month ($p > 0.05$ for all months), so that a normal distribution of the deltas can be assumed. Finally, the standard deviation of the deltas is calculated for each month.

For the Lümpenenbach catchment, the monthly mean values of the period 1982-2011 are calculated for both air temperature and humidity data recorded at the Erlenbach station. In order to simulate the future air temperature and relative humidity, the monthly delta of the SMHI resp. DMI simulation (future period – reference period) is added to the monthly mean value of the Erlenbach (period 1982-2011). The result represents the predicted monthly mean value of the future period (2021-2050) for the Lümpenenbach catchment. In a next step, random temperature and humidity values are generated for each day in the future which show the predicted monthly mean values over the entire future period (2021-2050). The distribution of the random values is restricted to the standard deviation of the deltas of the respective month of the SMHI resp. DMI simulation.

Eventually, the randomly generated values for future temperature and relative humidity are used to calculate daily wet-bulb temperatures for every day in the future (2021-2050). If the daily wet-bulb temperature is below $-3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the snowmaking capacity is calculated for a snow gun operation time of 12, 18 and 24 hours using the snow gun productivity values depicted in Figure 14.

For the analysis (both contemporary and future conditions), the daily snowmaking capacities (m^3) are summed up for the period 1st - 23rd of December for every year and related to the required snow volume for the preparation of the three ski slopes at Brunni-Haggenegg.

3.4.2 Simulation of natural snow cover

The natural snow availability needs to be determined in order to know how much snow is needed to complement natural snow shortages. Data on the natural snow cover has been previously generated with a 1D numerical model called COUP (Stähli & Gustafsson, 2006). Meteorological measurements recorded at the Erlenbach station have been used as input parameters including air temperature, wind speed, air humidity, precipitation and global radiation. The model output includes snow depth and snow water equivalent (SWE). The used model was previously validated by Stähli and Gustafsson (2006) and shows an overall convincing simulation of both snow parameters for the study area. Both output parameters are used to calculate the snow depth of a compacted ski slope. The SWE is divided by the snow depth resulting in

the snow density of the modelled snow. If snow density is lower than 400 kg/m^3 , the snow density is upscaled to 400 kg/m^3 by downscaling the snow depth, meaning the product of snow density and snow depth (i.e. the SWE) remains constant. The resulting snow depth is plotted over the months of November to end of March, in order to have an overview of the snow cover evolution during winter of different years. Hence, it becomes visible in which months snow-making is necessary to complement snow shortages. This is the case anytime the natural snow depth (density of 400 kg/m^3) is less than 40 cm.

3.4.3 Integration of snowmaking capacity and snow deficit in WEAP

In WEAP, the purpose of snowmaking is defined as a demand site in the model (cf. Figure 9), which allows the expression of a daily snow demand. Since it is particularly important to have intact ski slopes during Christmas holidays, water demand for snowmaking is limited to the period 01.12. - 23.12. (i.e. before Christmas). The daily snow demand is defined by the technical snowmaking capacity (cf. section 3.4.1). This means, anytime snow can be produced according to the meteorological conditions, water is demanded from the reservoir. However, once a maximum water volume (abbr. MWV) has been allocated to snowmaking, the daily demand is set to zero.

The maximum water volume is defined as follows:

$$MWV := \frac{SA * SD * SF}{SWR} \quad (4)$$

where:

SA = Ski slope area (m^2)

SF = Safety factor

SD = Snow depth (m)

SWR = Snow-water-ratio

The applied safety factor is based on the natural snow cover (cf. section 3.4.2) of the respective winter. There are two scenarios:

- A) In case the natural snow depth is less than 20 cm on December 24th, the maximum water volume is defined by the water volume necessary to produce a technical snow depth of 40 cm ($SWR = 2$) for all three slopes at Brunni-Haggenegg with a safety factor of 1.5 (i.e. tolerating losses of 33-50% through snowmelt).

$$MWV_A := \frac{(19160 + 15580 + 18340) * 0.4 * 1.5}{2} = 15'924 \text{ m}^3$$

- B) If the natural snow depth is more than 20 cm on December 24th, the maximum water volume is defined analogous but with a safety factor of 1.

$$MWV_B := \frac{(19160 + 15580 + 18340) * 0.4 * 1}{2} = 10'161 \text{ m}^3$$

The safety factor is applied because snowmelt cannot be taken into account. In case the MWV is reached before December 24th, it is assumed that there is enough snow during Christmas holidays for all slopes. Thus, it is analyzed in which years of the past decade the MWV is reached with a hypothetical reservoir by considering different reservoir sizes.

3.5 Other uses

3.5.1 Artificial flood experiments

Due to the availability of hydrological and meteorological data, the upper catchment area of the Alptal has served as study area for a diverse range of research projects investigating runoff generation and groundwater interaction, bedrock erosion and sediment transport, snow hydrology etc. (Badoux et al., 2012; Gustafsson et al., 2004; Masteller et al., 2019; Rinderer et al., 2016; Van Meerveld et al., 2018). The benefit of a reservoir with respect to research consists in the possibility of releasing a large volume of water upon request and increasing natural streamflow above thresholds where erosion and sediment transport processes become active. While the prediction of flood events in alpine areas is challenging (cf. Liechti et al., 2013; Schaepli et al., 2007; Sikorska & Seibert, 2018; Verbunt et al., 2007), the generation of artificial floods on predefined dates would allow the installation of measuring instruments prior to the event, providing high resolution data to be recorded during the event. Furthermore, the standard resolution of the Lümpenenbach streamflow gauge is currently limited to 10 minutes for data management reasons. During an artificial flood event, however, the resolution could be increased manually to generate data points every second or every minute, resulting in a precise hydrograph of the event. Consequently, artificial flood experiments could extend research possibilities in fields related to the morphology and control of torrents.

Since research applications are diverse, the evaluation of this purpose focuses on the water volumes that can be generated with the reservoir and not on the numerous benefits these water volumes may have for specific research fields. Thus, it is analyzed which extreme streamflow intensities can be generated for how many hours with different reservoir volumes. The streamflow intensities to be analyzed are determined by a generalized extreme value distribution (GEV) using the data of the Lümpenenbach streamflow gauge (10min resolution). The yearly maxima of the period 1985-2019 are determined and used to calculate a GEV using the R package “gevXgpd” (Frey, 2010). For the analysis, flood intensities of the return periods 5, 10, 30, 100 and 300 years are considered.

In WEAP, the purpose of artificial flood experiments is integrated with the flow requirement “AFE” (cf. Figure 9). Importantly, during an artificial flood event the entire volume of the reservoir is released into the Lümpenenbach on a single day. Since the model works on a daily resolution, this effect can be achieved by setting the flow requirement to 5 m³/s. Unlike other purposes, the benefit of artificial flood experiments is not restricted to specific months of the year. Therefore, it is reasonable to conduct them when the water demand of other water users

is lowest, which is the case during spring and autumn (cf. section 3.6). Thus, the flow requirement is activated for one day at the beginning of April, May and September. As flood experiments empty the reservoir storage completely, the time to refill the reservoir after every experiment is analyzed for every month separately (years 2009-2019).

3.5.2 Flood retention

As flood intensity and frequency are projected to increase because of climate change (CH2018, 2018), flood retention measures gain in importance. In this context, reservoirs can be used to attenuate flood peaks (Kellner & Weingartner, 2018). The natural hazard map of the municipality of Alpthal-Brunni (cf. Figure A 5 in Appendix A), however, shows a low risk of flooding within the Lümpebach catchment (Canton of Schwyz, 2020). Zones classified as intermediate risk zones only affect few isolated buildings, whereas most zones only affect agricultural land. Thus, indications for future destructive floods and a direct benefit of flood retention measures are missing. Therefore, the potential of the reservoir to retain floods is considered on a theoretical basis. It is analyzed for how many hours a reservoir could retain an extreme flood of the return periods 5, 10, 30, 100 and 300 years. Hence, the theoretical retention capacity of the reservoir is equal to the capacity for artificial flood generation explained in section 3.5.1.

In contrast to artificial flood experiments, flood retention results in an increase in reservoir storage. Since we focus on the theoretical retention capacity and not on real events of the Lümpebach time series, this purpose is not integrated in the reservoir simulation model.

3.5.3 Recreational activities and tourism

Reservoirs can be regarded as lakes. Thus, they may serve for recreational activities and promote hiking tourism. According to the Swiss tourism association (STV, 2020), tourism is most active in the months of July and August, hence the benefit of a reservoir lake should be highest during this period. Moreover, tourism may be more active during school holidays in spring and public holidays such as Easter. For this thesis, it is suggested that 80% of the reservoir storage needs to be filled with water in order to attract people to the reservoir. This percentage is not motivated by a specific reason since the perception of a full reservoir lake highly depends on the reservoir's floor plan and volume-elevation curve. Since the elaboration of the reservoir's architecture is beyond the scope of this thesis, the value of 80% is taken as a first pragmatic approximation.

The touristic purpose of the reservoir is integrated in WEAP by setting the inactive volume of the reservoir to 80% of the reservoir storage capacity from mid-April to end of April (representing spring holidays) and during the entire month of July (school holidays in summer). Hence, only up to 20% of the reservoir volume can be used for water allocation during these periods. This may have a negative effect on the purpose of streamflow augmentation for brown trout. The evaluation of trade-offs between different purposes is discussed in the following section.

3.6 Handling trade-offs

The benefit of the reservoir is for some purposes restricted to specific months and seasons, whereas for others it is not time dependent. As a consequence, there are conflicting uses which are depicted in Table 6. Flood retention is divided into two purposes, one is linked to the spawning and incubation season of brown trout (cf. section 3.3.2). The other purpose considers the theoretical retention capacity of the reservoir (cf. section 3.5.2), which can be required anytime during the year. Since flood retention results in a rapid increase in reservoir storage, no negative effects on the other purposes are expected.

Table 6: Time dependency of the benefit for different purposes of the reservoir. Δ Storage indicates the change in reservoir volume (+ = increase, - = decrease, 0 = no change) of the respective uses. Red symbol borders show conflicting uses.

Water use / Purpose	Δ Storage	Jan.	Feb.	March	April	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.	
Flood retention for brown trout	+	[Yellow bar]									[Yellow bar]			
Provision of minimum flow for brown trout	-	[Yellow bar with red border]												
Snowmaking	-	[Blue bar with red border]											[Blue bar with red border]	
Recreational activities /tourism	0				[Green box]			[Green box]						
Artificial flood experiments	-				[Pink box]	[Pink box]				[Pink box]				
Flood retention	+	[Grey bar]												

The benefits of snowmaking, recreational activities and flood retention to protect offspring of brown trout are limited to specific months of the year (cf. sections 3.3.2, 3.4 and 3.5.3). The benefit of artificial flood experiments, however, is not time dependent. Hence, the period of the year showing the fewest conflicts can be selected, which are the months of April, May and September. Artificial floods empty the reservoir completely. Thus, the time to refill the reservoir needs to be considered, because low flow conditions may require additional water release for brown trout anytime during the year. Since discharge is highest during spring months (cf. section 2.2), the generation of artificial floods may be less conflicting in the months of April and May. This assumption is analyzed by evaluating the trade-off between artificial flood experiments and the provision of a minimum flow for brown trout for every month separately.

In addition, artificial flood experiments may have a negative effect on tourism. As the second half of April is defined as spring holidays, the reservoir should be filled by 80% in order to benefit hiking tourism. Therefore, it will be analyzed whether artificial flood experiments at the beginning of April are possible without negatively affecting recreational activities. The same potential conflict is analyzed for artificial flood experiments at the beginning of May and recreational activities starting in July.

The provision of a minimum flow for brown trout may become necessary anytime during the year. Therefore, this purpose marks a fundamental source of conflict. Importantly, low water levels are less likely in spring due to snowmelt in the area (Gustafsson et al., 2004; Keller et al., 2004). Thus, trade-offs are more likely to occur in summer with tourism, in autumn with artificial flood experiments and in winter with snowmaking.

These trade-offs are assessed as follows. First, the reservoir's benefit for every purpose is analyzed in a single-purpose reservoir system. In WEAP, this is achieved by deactivating all other purposes. Then, the reservoir's potential for every benefit is analyzed a second time in a multi-purpose reservoir system where the conflicting purposes are active. Consequently, the trade-off between two purposes is evaluated by considering the reduction of the benefit for each purpose in the multi-purpose reservoir system compared to the benefit in the single-purpose reservoir system. The trade-offs will be analyzed for all mentioned conflicting uses.

4. Results

4.1 Improving streamflow conditions for brown trout populations

4.1.1 Augmentation of low streamflow

In the following, the results concerning the reservoir's capacity to augment low streamflow are presented. Figure 15 summarizes the number of days with discharge values below the minimum flow requirement (MFR) of 150 l/s and 200 l/s in Alpthal during the period 2009-2019 (11 years). For both flow requirements, the number of days with values below the MFR decreases with increasing reservoir size.

Figure 15: Total number of days with streamflow values below the minimum flow requirement of a) 150 l/s, b) 200 l/s in Alpthal. Shown is the period 2009-2019 (11 years). The number of days is evaluated for different reservoir sizes (x-axis) and the two reservoir locations Brüschrain (yellow) and Nättschberg (blue).

For a MFR of 150 l/s in Alpthal (Figure 15a), a reservoir size of 5'000 m³ can reduce the number of days by 20%, one of 100'000 m³ by more than 75%. This indicates a non-linear and rather logarithmic relationship between the reduction in number of days and reservoir volume. Thus, the largest reduction (per m³ volume) is already achieved with the reservoir size of 5'000 m³; from 349 days (reference scenario) to 279 days (Brüschrain scenario) resp. 276 days (Nätschberg scenario). The differences between the two reservoir sites are marginal for small reservoir sizes and increase with larger reservoir volumes; a reservoir of 100'000 m³ located at Brüschrain can decrease the number to 103 days, while located at Nätschberg the number can be reduced to 82 days.

For a MFR of 200 l/s (Figure 15b), the values are twice as large, but the same patterns can be observed. The relationship between reservoir size and reduction in number of days is decreasing with reservoir size; the largest reduction (per m³ volume) is reached with a reservoir size of 5'000 m³ from 744 to 569 days (Brüschrain) resp. 566 days (Nätschberg). The relative reduction compared to the reference scenario (no reservoir) is around 25% for a reservoir size of 5'000 m³ and 65% for a volume of 100'000 m³. The differences with respect to reservoir location are marginal for small reservoirs and increase with reservoir size. Notably, the corresponding flow requirements of 90 l/s resp. 110 l/s in Brunni show very similar values and equal patterns (cf. Figure A 14 in Appendix E).

Due to the similarity of results with respect to the two different reservoir locations, the following paragraphs focus on a reservoir located at Nätschberg. Similarly, the further analysis is limited to the flow requirements in Alpthal, as the deviations to the results of the flow requirements in Brunni are negligible.

Figure 16: As Figure 15A but showing monthly resolution and only for Nätschberg. The bars represent absolute numbers for the period 2009-2019, colours represent different reservoir volumes (m³).

Figure 16 shows the number of days with discharge values below the minimum flow requirement of 150 l/s in Alpthal on a monthly basis (period 2009-2019). In the months of February to May, the streamflow is less than 10 times below the MFR during the entire period. Consequently, the number is reduced to zero with a reservoir size of 30'000 m³ (except for February). In the months of May to July and October to December, the reduction in number of days is increasing with reservoir size. Notably, this relationship is not valid for all reservoir sizes in the months of August, September and January. For instance, in September the reduction in number of days is increasing until a reservoir size of 30'000 m³, whereas larger reservoirs (50'000 and 100'000 m³) do not achieve any further decline. The same effect is detectable in August for reservoir sizes between 15'000 and 50'000 m³. The months of July to January show values between 20 and 80 days in the reference scenario, indicating discharge values below the MFR on 2 to 8 days per month on average. This conclusion, however, is not valid, which is explained in the following. The pattern for the higher flow requirement of 200 l/s in Alpthal is very similar (cf. Figure A 15 in Appendix E) and is therefore not commented.

Figure 17 depicts the water volume that is missing to meet the MFR of 150 l/s in Alpthal for the three longest periods (i.e. number of consecutive days on which the MFR is not reached) per year. It can be stated that in some years (e.g. 2010, 2012-2014), the missing volume is almost equal to zero. This demonstrates that in these years, the discharge never/rarely drops below the MFR. Moreover, in many years (e.g. 2009, 2016, 2017, 2019) the second and/or third longest period show a missing volume of nearly zero. Hence, in these years only one or two low flow periods are occurring.

Figure 17: Missing water volume (without reservoir contribution) to meet the minimum flow requirement (MFR) of 150 l/s in Alpthal. Longest periods < MFR are defined as the largest number of consecutive days with streamflow values < MFR in Alpthal in the reference scenario (no reservoir).

In the years 2016 and 2018, the missing volume exceeds 100'000 m³, thus even a reservoir storage of 100'000 m³ could not augment the streamflow sufficiently. By contrast, the graphic illustrates that a reservoir storage of 50'000 m³ can cope with the second longest period in all years except 2018.

An aspect not detectable in Figure 17 is the distribution of the low flow periods, i.e. in which months these periods occur. In case the longest and second longest period occur in the same or in successive months, the reservoir's potential to augment streamflow may be overestimated in the graph. This phenomenon is illustrated in Figure 18, where the streamflow of the Alp in Alpthal is depicted with and without reservoir contribution from July to December 2015. In summer 2015, there are several weeks in which natural streamflow of the Alp is below 150 l/s in Alpthal; from July 9th to 18th and 21st to 26th. Consequently, water is released from the reservoir (initial storage of 50'000 m³) and succeeding in augmenting streamflow until July 24th. After this date, the reservoir is empty and the streamflow with and without reservoir is equal. Therefore, the potential of the reservoir to augment streamflow at the beginning of August (July 31st to August 14th) is zero. Towards the end of August, the reservoir is refilled with a water volume of 15'000 m³, which is released during the following low flow period (August 23rd to 29th). Hence, in August 2015 the potential of a reservoir with 15'000 m³ is equal to one with a volume of 50'000 m³. The same effect can be observed in November 2018 (cf. Figure A 16 in Appendix E).

Figure 18: Streamflow evolution of the Alp in Alpthal from July-December 2015 with and without reservoir (y-axis on the left) and corresponding evolution of the reservoir storage (y-axis on the right).

4.1.2 Reduction of critical flood levels

In the following section, the reservoir's capacity to retain critical floods (i.e. floods involving bedload transport) for the months of October to March is evaluated. Figure 19 shows the number of days with discharge values above the critical flood level (CFL) in Brunni for the period 2009-2019. The retention capacity of the reservoir is small in either location: Of 64 critical floods only 5 can be attenuated sufficiently with a reservoir located at Brüschrain and 13 if

located at Nättschberg. Hence, the reservoir’s capacity for flood retention is higher for the Nättschberg location. The capacity of the reservoir to attenuate critical flood levels in Alpthal is smaller than in Brunnli; of 82 critical floods, 2 events can be retained with a reservoir at Brüschrain and 3 events if located at Nättschberg, respectively (cf. Figure A 18 in Appendix E).

Figure 19: Number of days with streamflow above the critical flood level (CFR) of 1.39 m³/s in Brunnli during the period 2009-2019 (11 years). Values are calculated for the reference scenario (no reservoir) and for the reservoir locations Brüschrain and Nättschberg (unlimited reservoir size).

Despite the low capacity of the reservoir to attenuate floods sufficiently, the reservoir size to exploit the full potential is of interest. Table 7 depicts the water volumes abstracted from the Lümpepenbach to the reservoir during successful flood retention events. Successful flood retention events are defined as events where the reservoir can attenuate the streamflow below the critical flood level of 1,39 m³/s in Brunnli resp. 2,09 m³/s in Alpthal. The presented values are the maximum sums of 1, 3 and 7 consecutive days of the period 2009-2019. The values are larger in Nättschberg than in Brüschrain. In order to exploit the complete potential for flood retention on a daily basis, a vacant storage of 9'950 m³ is necessary in Brüschrain and 25'330 m³ in Nättschberg, respectively. The required storage is increased to 12'560 m³ in Brüschrain and 47'260 m³ in Nättschberg when considering successful flood attenuation events of 3 consecutive days. The latter does not change for a period of 7 days, whereas the required storage in Brüschrain increases to 18'000 m³.

Table 7: Required vacant reservoir storage for the exploitation of the full flood retention potential. The values represent the maximum water volumes (m³) abstracted to the reservoir during successful flood attenuation events of 1, 3 and 7 consecutive days for the period 2009-2019.

	1 day	3 days	7 days
Brüschrain	9'950 m³	12'560 m³	18'000 m³
Nättschberg	25'330 m³	47'260 m³	47'260 m³

4.2 Snowmaking at Brunni-Haggenegg

4.2.1 Snowmaking capacity

Figure 20 illustrates the technical snowmaking capacity for the period 01.12.-23.12. of the years 2004-2019 (16 years). The snowmaking capacity of the snow guns at Brunni-Haggenegg exceeds the snow volume needed for the preparation of the three ski slopes in all years except 2014, 2015 and 2019. In 2014 the snowmaking capacity can provide the snow volume for one ski slope, whereas in 2019 hardly any snowmaking is possible before Christmas.

Figure 20: Technical snowmaking capacity for the years 2004-2019 using meteorological data recorded at the Erlenbach station (hourly resolution). Snow volume refers to technical snow with a density of approx. 400 kg/m^3 .

Regarding future climate conditions, the respective snowmaking capacities (period 01.12.-23.12.) for the SMHI-RCA4-EC-EARTH and DMI-HIRHAM-EC-EARTH simulations are depicted in Figure 21. Importantly, the numbers on the x-axis do not reflect specific years but represent the prediction for snowmaking by the RCP8.5 scenario around 2035. The snowmaking capacity is illustrated for three different calculations: As daily mean values have been used to calculate the daily wet-bulb temperature, the corresponding snowmaking capacity has been calculated for a daily snow production of 12, 18 and 24 hours.

In the SMHI-RCA4-EC-EARTH simulation, the snowmaking capacity of the 12h assumption does not exceed the snow volume required for the preparation of all three slopes in any winter (0%). In 15 of 30 winters (50%), the capacity reaches the snow volume needed for one ski slope. Regarding the 18h assumption, the capacity is higher than the required snow volume for all slopes in 6 winters (20%) and for one slope in 24 winters (80%). Concerning the

Results

24h assumption, the snowmaking capacity exceeds the snow volume for all slopes in 10 of 30 winters (33%).

In comparison, the DMI-HIRHAM-EC-EARTH simulation shows higher values for all three assumptions. In 21 (24h assumption) resp. 16 (18h assumption) of 30 winters ($> 50\%$), the snowmaking capacity is higher than the snow volume necessary to prepare all slopes. With the 12h assumption, a snow volume for 1 slope can be provided in 25 of 30 winters (83%).

Figure 21: Technical snowmaking capacity of a) the SMHI-RCA4-EC-EARTH simulation and b) the DMI-HIRHAM-EC-EARTH simulation. Both calculated for a daily snow gun operation of 12, 18 and 24 hours (RCP8.5 scenario, period 2021-2050). Snow volume refers to technical snow with a density of approx. 400 kg/m^3 .

Importantly, the values in Figure 20 cannot be compared to the ones in Figure 21, as in the former meteorological data of hourly (not daily) resolution was used. For a direct comparison Figure A 19 in Appendix E can be consulted.

4.2.2 Natural snow cover modelled in COUP

The evolution of the snow depth (with a density of 400 kg/m^3) of the Lümpenenbach catchment is displayed in Figure 22. The natural snow depth exceeds 40 cm over Christmas holidays in 4 winters (2010/11, 2011/12, 2012/13, 2017/18), and in 2 winters (2009/10 and 2014/15) it is higher than 20 cm. In the winters 2015/16 and 2016/17, there is a natural snow depth of more than 20 cm in the middle and towards the end of November which melts entirely until Christmas holidays. After Christmas holidays, the natural snow depth increases in most winters and total melt losses are generally limited to 20 cm until the end of February.

Figure 22: Calculated snow depth (snow density of 400 kg/m^3) for the Lümpenenbach catchment for the winter seasons 2009/10 – 2018/19 using SWE and snow depth data provided by the COUP model.

4.2.3 Combination of snowmaking capacity and natural snow cover

The natural snow cover is taken into account to predict the required amount to be contributed by snowmaking before Christmas for every year (cf. section 3.4.3). Following the natural snow availability in Figure 22, the required amounts of water for adequate snowmaking are:

- $15'924 \text{ m}^3$ in December 2013, 2014, 2015, 2016, 2018 and 2019
- $10'161 \text{ m}^3$ in December 2009, 2010, 2011, 2012 and 2017

As previously commented (cf. Figure 20), the snowmaking capacity enables sufficient snow production in all years except 2014, 2015 and 2019 (i.e. 8 years in total). Consequently, in the other years, not the meteorological conditions but the reservoir size is the limiting factor. Figure 23 displays the unmet water demand for snowmaking of the years 2009-2019 for

different reservoir sizes located at Nätschberg. Unmet demand is defined as the missing water volume to take full advantage of the technical snowmaking capacity (for producing the snow volumes required to prepare all three ski slopes). With a reservoir volume of 5'000 m³, there is a missing water volume of more than 3'000 m³ in 4 of the 8 respective winters (50%). A reservoir size of 10'000 m³ cannot meet the water demand in 2 of the 8 respective winters (25%). With a reservoir size of 15'000 m³, there is no unmet demand in any of the analyzed years. A similar result is obtained for a reservoir located at Brüschrain (cf. Figure A 20 in Appendix E).

Figure 23: Unmet water demand for snowmaking considering different reservoir sizes at the Nätschberg location.

4.3 Artificial flood experiments and theoretical flood retention capacity

Figure 24 shows the maximum duration of artificial flood experiments with discharge intensities of different return periods. The return periods have been calculated using a GEV distribution, the relationship between measured and fitted values is illustrated in Figure A 21 in Appendix E. A reservoir with a volume of 5'000 m³ can generate a 5-year flood (i.e. 2.78 m³/s) for half an hour, with a volume of 50'000 m³ it can be maintained for 5 hours. Hence, the relationship between reservoir size and duration of floods is linear. Notably, even a reservoir with a moderate volume of 5'000 m³ would allow the generation of a 100-year flood event for about 20 minutes. The values in Figure 24 also represent the theoretical flood retention capacity (cf. section 3.5.2) of the reservoir.

Figure 24: Maximum duration of artificial flood experiments generating streamflow intensities of different return periods dependent on different reservoir volumes.

Regarding real flood events measured at the Lämpenenbach streamflow gauge (Table 8), a reservoir of 30'000 m³ may simulate any of the listed flood events in terms of water volume. This includes the largest flood event ever recorded ($Q_{max}=3.82$ m³/s) of the year 1987. The flood event of 2007 caused the highest discharge since 2000. The discharge hydrographs of the different flood events are depicted in Figure A 22 in Appendix E.

Table 8: Water volumes of yearly flood events of different years: 1987 (highest Q_{max} since beginning of records), 2007 (highest Q_{max} since 2000), 2018 (moderate HQ_{max}) and 2019 (high HQ_{max}).

Year	Duration [h]	Max Q measured [m ³ /s]	Water volume above 50 l/s [m ³]
1987	17	3.82	27'012
2007	20	2.90	29'811
2018	16	1.91	10'829
2019	21	2.59	26'812

The conduction of artificial flood experiments has a major effect on reservoir storage, so that the refilling time needs to be considered. Figure 25 displays the number of days required to refill a reservoir at Brüschrain and Nätschberg during different months.

Figure 25: Refilling time (expressed in number of days) after releasing the entire volume (i.e. storage = 0) of a a) Nätschberg reservoir, b) Brüschrain reservoir. Boxplots generated using data of the years 2010-2019.

For a reservoir located at Nätschberg, refilling water volumes of 15'000 and 30'000 m³ at the beginning of April and May is generally limited to 12 days. For experiments conducted at the beginning of September, the refilling time for water volumes of 15'000 m³ is in most years restricted to less than 15 days, and for 30'000 m³ to less than 22 days, respectively. Hence, the refilling time for a reservoir storage of 30'000 m³ is up to 10 days longer in September than in spring. Concerning water volumes of 50'000 m³, refilling requires up to 32 days in April (except 1 outlier), up to 35 days in May and up to 50 days in September. Thus, the refilling period for experiments using a water volume of 50'000 m³ may take 1-2 months.

For a Brüschrain reservoir, the refilling period after artificial flood experiments in April is prolonged by around 5-10 days compared to the Nätschberg location. In May, the refilling period is within a range of 8 to 48 days for a volume of 30'000 m³ and thus remarkably longer than for a volume of 15'000 m³. In September, the reservoir can be refilled with 15'000 m³ within 22 days (except 1 outlier), whereas obtaining larger storages of 30'000 and 50'000 m³ requires up to 60 and 94 days, respectively.

4.4 Trade-offs

The results considering the trade-offs between different purposes are very similar for both reservoir locations. Therefore, the following sections will present the results for a reservoir located at Brüschrain.

4.4.1 Trade-off between snowmaking and streamflow augmentation for brown trout

As illustrated in Table 6 (cf. section 3.6), the purposes of snowmaking and augmentation of low streamflow for brown trout may overlap in time. Figure 26 depicts this trade-off from the perspective of brown trout's vital interests. With a reservoir size of 15'000 m³, the number of days with streamflow values below 150 l/s in Alpthal can be reduced from 84 days to 60 days if streamflow augmentation is the only purpose of the reservoir. In case of a multi-purpose usage involving the purpose of snowmaking, the number can be reduced to 65 days. Hence, there is a trade-off during 5 days on which streamflow augmentation is not possible due to snowmaking. This trade-off is slightly reduced with increasing reservoir size; for a reservoir volume of 50'000 m³, the difference between the single-purpose and multi-purpose system consists in 3 days only. The trade-off between snowmaking and streamflow augmentation is similar for the higher flow requirement of 200 l/s in Alpthal (cf. Figure A 23 in Appendix E) independent of the reservoir location.

Figure 26: Trade-off between snowmaking and augmentation of low streamflow from the perspective of brown trout. Shown is the number of days with discharge values below 150 l/s in Alpthal (period 2009-2019, winter season) in a single purpose reservoir system (brown trout only) and multi-purpose reservoir system (brown trout and snowmaking). Reservoir location: Brüschrain.

Table 9 illustrates the trade-off from the perspective of snowmaking. As previously stated in section 4.2.3 (cf. Figure 23), in a single-purpose reservoir system, there is no unmet demand for snowmaking with a reservoir storage of 15'000 m³. Table 9 displays the unmet demand for

snowmaking in a multi-purpose reservoir system, i.e. when the reservoir benefits snowmaking and brown trout simultaneously. In most years, there is no unmet demand for a volume of 15'000 m³, meaning there is no trade-off between the two purposes. In 2011 and 2016, there is an unmet demand for every displayed reservoir volume. While the unmet demand is reduced with increasing reservoir size in 2016, this effect cannot be observed in 2011. A low flow period (i.e. streamflow below the MFR 90 l/s in Brünni and/or 150 l/s in Alpthal) comprising several weeks in November 2011 is the reason for this (cf. Figure A 17 in Appendix E). Hence, the reservoir storage is zero at the beginning of December causing an unmet demand regardless of the actual reservoir size.

Table 9: Trade-off between snowmaking and augmentation of low streamflow (MFR of 90l/s in Brünni and 150 l/s in Alpthal). Trade-off expressed as missing water volume [m³] for snowmaking for different reservoir volumes at Brüschrain. Non-displayed years from 2009-2019 do not show missing water volumes (no trade-off).

Vol. Res. \ Year	2011	2013	2016
15'000 m ³	6'247	253	1'496
30'000 m ³	6'247	0	1'191
50'000 m ³	6'247	0	443

In order to avoid an empty reservoir, the time to fill the reservoir with a water volume of 15'000 m³ before the 1st of December is depicted in Figure 27 for the years 2009-2019. In 9 of 11 years, a reservoir located at Brüschrain is filled within 28 days and at Nättschberg within 20 days. Median values are 19 days for Brüschrain and 13 days for Nättschberg.

Figure 27: Number of days to fill a reservoir with 15'000 m³ water before the 1st of December. Data considered from 2009-2019.

4.4.2 Trade-off between tourism and streamflow augmentation for brown trout

In the following, the trade-off between tourism and streamflow augmentation for brown trout is considered. Tourism is a special purpose as, unlike the other purposes, the benefit for tourism is depending on a large reservoir storage and not on the release of water. Hence, it is important to have a filled reservoir at the beginning of summer holidays. Figure 28 illustrates the number of days required to fill a reservoir of different volumes by 80% before the 1st of July. For a Brüschrain reservoir, less than 20 days are required to fill a reservoir of 15'000 m³ by 80%, whereas larger volumes of 30'000 m³ and 50'000 m³ may take up to 40 and 50 days, respectively. By contrast, the filling of a Nätschberg reservoir does not take more than 30 days in any year (period 2009-2019).

Figure 28: Time to fill a reservoir by 80% of its storage capacity before the 1st of July calculated for the period 2009-2019.

Figure 29 shows the number of days with discharge values below 150 l/s in Alpthal for both a single-purpose and multi-purpose reservoir system. If the reservoir's only purpose is the augmentation of low streamflow, the reduction in number of days is higher in July than in August. Moreover, in July the potential is increasing with reservoir size, whereas in August this effect is not visible (cf. section 4.1.1). In the multi-purpose reservoir scenario, water release is limited to 20% of the reservoir size during July because of tourism. Hence, the potential to augment low streamflow is smaller in July. Interestingly, this negative effect is partially compensated in August, as the reduction in number of days below the MFR is higher in the multi-purpose scenario than in the single-purpose scenario. Table 10 summarizes the number of days depicted in Figure 29. It reveals a trade-off on 4 days for a reservoir volume of 15'000 m³, which is increasing to 6 days for larger volumes (30'000 m³ and 50'000 m³). Similar results are obtained for the higher flow requirement of 200 l/s in Alpthal for a reservoir located at Nätschberg (cf. Figure A 24 in Appendix E).

Figure 29: Number of days with streamflow values below 150 l/s in Alpthal during the period 2009-2019 with a single-purpose reservoir (brown trout only) and a multi-purpose reservoir (brown trout and tourism) located at Brüschrain.

Table 10: Trade-off between tourism and streamflow augmentation for brown trout (BT). Shown is the number of days with streamflow values below 150 l/s in Alpthal for a single-purpose reservoir (BT only) and multi-purpose reservoir (BT and tourism) located at Brüschrain during the months of July and August (period 2009-2019).

Reservoir size	BT only July + August	BT & tourism July + August	Trade-off
15'000 m ³	74	78	4
30'000 m ³	66	72	6
50'000 m ³	56	62	6

4.4.3 Trade-off between artificial flood experiments and streamflow augmentation for brown trout

The effect of artificial flood experiments at the beginning of April, May and September on the augmentation of low streamflow for brown trout (MFR 150 l/s in Alpthal) is limited to the months of May and September. In successive months (June/July and October/November) there is no trade-off as there is no difference in the number of days with streamflow values below the MFR between the multi-purpose reservoir and single-purpose reservoir system (not shown). The trade-off in the months of May and September is illustrated in Figure 30. The trade-off is assessed for three different types of artificial flood experiments. If the reservoir storage is emptied entirely, the number of days can only be reduced from 7 to 6 days, whereas in the single-purpose reservoir system it can be reduced to 1 day. Thus, there is a trade-off on 5 days on which streamflow augmentation is not possible because of artificial flood experiments. In September, there is a trade-off on 2 days. In both months, the trade-off can be reduced by keeping a certain water volume in the reservoir. If the remaining water volume is 1'000 m³, there is a trade-off on 4 days in May and on 1 day in September. With a remaining volume of 5'000 m³, no trade-off is detectable in September. Notably, in September the negative effects resulting from artificial flood experiments are very small compared to the situation without reservoir, whereas absolute numbers in May are already small taking into account that they cover a period of 11 years. The trade-off is of similar relative range even if the higher flow requirement of 200 l/s in Alpthal is considered for a Nättschberg reservoir (cf. Figure A 25 in Appendix E).

Figure 30: Trade-off between artificial flood experiments (AFE) and augmentation of low streamflow for brown trout (BT) from the perspective of brown trout. Shown is the number of days with discharge values below 150 l/s in Alpthal (period 2009-2019, months May and September) in a single purpose reservoir system (BT only) and multi-purpose reservoir system (BT and AFE). Number in brackets show the remaining reservoir storage after an artificial flood experiment. Reservoir location: Brüschrain.

5. Discussion

Hereafter, we first discuss the model set-up (section 5.1), before discussing in detail the research questions about the potential of the reservoir to improve streamflow conditions for brown trout (section 5.2), followed by the potential benefit for snowmaking (section 5.3) and the formulation of management rules and the suggestion of an adequate reservoir size (section 5.4 and 5.5).

5.1 Estimation of local water availability from streamflow gauges downstream

The estimation of local water availability (at high temporal resolution) to simulate reservoir filling processes was a major challenge and cornerstone for the study. As water flow in the WEAP model relies on measured streamflow data of two stations, a substantial simplification has been achieved by downscaling the measured streamflow area-based to different subcatchments. Thus, the percentage contribution of each subcatchment to streamflow remains constant over time. In reality, however, the streamflow contribution of different reaches is likely to vary, especially during precipitation events with large spatial variability in rainfall sum (Fischer et al., 2017). The varying contribution of certain reaches to the discharge measured at the Lümpebach station has also become visible during the field measurements at Brüschrain (53% and 47% at baseflow and 24% at the beginning of high flow, cf. Table 3). Interestingly, the results between a Brüschrain and a Nätschberg reservoir are within a similar range for all purposes (e.g. cf. Figure 15), even though the water availability for water abstraction to the reservoir was assumed twice as high in Nätschberg (80% of the Lümpebach) as in Brüschrain (40% of the Lümpebach). Thus, the similarity of the results indicate that the effect of this area-based simplification can be neglected for the Lümpebach catchment.

Concerning the Alp, the area-based downscaling of streamflow data of Einsiedeln is likely to underestimate streamflow in Brunni and Alpthal, because the specific runoff in Brunni is higher than in Einsiedeln (Einsiedeln: 1498 mm/year, Lümpebach catchment: 2016 mm/year, data 1988-2017). As a consequence, the contribution of the Lümpebach to the discharge in Brunni resp. Alpthal is overestimated in the simulation model (because the Lümpebach is simulated with measured data of the Lümpebach streamflow gauge). The natural contribution of the Lümpebach to the streamflow in the Alp, however, is only relevant for the evaluation of the retention capacity of critical floods (cf. section 4.1.2), whereas the analysis of other purposes is not affected.

5.2 Potential to improve streamflow conditions for brown trout

For the improvement of streamflow conditions for brown trout populations in the Alp, the reservoir's potential to augment low streamflow has been tested. An augmentation of low streamflow above the minimum flow requirement (MFR) of 90 l/s in Brunni resp. 150 l/s in Alpthal can be achieved on 20% (reservoir size 5'000 m³) to 75% (reservoir size 100'000 m³) of the days (cf. Figure 15). The latter indicates a striking difference to the present situation without reservoir and thereby a remarkable potential. The largest reduction (per m³ volume), however, is already achieved with the smallest reservoir size tested (5'000 m³). Hence, the observed reduction in number of days is mainly linked to the augmentation of streamflow on single days or short periods and/or periods with discharge values only slightly below the MFR. Periods that are likely to induce stress in brown trout, however, are characterized by many consecutive days of low streamflow (Alonso-González et al., 2008), such as in summer 2015 and 2018. Remarkably, in both summers a reservoir of 100'000 m³ can only augment the streamflow for some weeks but is not able to keep the streamflow above the MFR over the entire summer season (cf. Figure 17, Figure 18 and Figure A 16 in Appendix E). Hence, despite the remarkable reduction in number of days, the reservoir's potential to alleviate hydrological stress for brown trout needs to be considered with caution due to the limited potential during dry summers (e.g. 2015, 2018) and dry winters (e.g. 2011).

Furthermore, the MFR has been calculated following a statistical approach. Due to the lack of extensive field measurements in the Alp channel, it is not known whether the analyzed MFRs really represent thresholds for problematic stress levels in brown trout. Interestingly, the higher flow requirement of 110 l/s (Brunni) resp. 200 l/s (Alpthal) shows a very similar pattern in relative reduction in number of days below the MFR for different reservoir sizes (cf. Figure 15 and Figure A 14 in Appendix E). Furthermore, the capacity to augment streamflow in different years (esp. summer 2015, 2018, winter 2011) is similar, even though absolute values are almost twice as high (not shown). This may indicate that despite the uncertainty of the thresholds, the capacity pattern of reservoirs of different sizes for slightly higher or lower thresholds may not change. Nevertheless, more elaborated methods (e.g. a hydrological model of the riverbed of the Alp section or field measurements of water depth and velocity across various cross-sections at different discharge conditions) (cf. Dönni et al., 2016) could provide more reliable thresholds and thus more reliable results.

Concerning reservoir sizes, during long periods of low flow reservoir filling is limited to small or moderate volumes (15'000 m³ in August 2015 and November 2018, 40'000 m³ from September to December 2015) (cf. Figure 18 and Figure A 16). Hence, larger reservoirs (> 50'000 m³) only show a higher potential for streamflow augmentation at the beginning of low flow periods. Once the storage is empty, their capacity for streamflow augmentation in subsequent months is equal to the one of reservoirs of smaller volumes.

As the reservoir's capacity for a continuous augmentation of streamflow is moderate for periods comprising several weeks, an alternative management strategy may be considered. For instance, the reservoir's potential increases if the minimum flow is only provided during certain intervals (e.g. every second/third day or once a week). This temporary increase in streamflow might still reduce hydrological stress for brown trout in the Alp. In addition, the reservoir could be used to simulate small floods by releasing larger volumes (e.g. 2'000 m³) in times where streamflow variability is low due to lack of precipitation. Such events might remove algae, which tend to reduce fish movement (J.K. personal communication 14.03.2020). Moreover, fishes which are trapped in water pools might access other spots due to these events. Depending on the magnitude of the flood, the impact is not restricted to the section of the Alp between Brunni and Alpthal but even brown trout in the Alp near Einsiedeln may benefit. Furthermore, the brown trout is an indicator fish species for ecological functioning of streams (FOEN, 2004). Hence, other riverine organisms would possibly benefit from stress reduction as well. Although the positive effects of intermittent augmentation of streamflow may be diverse, studies supporting the advantages of streamflow variability for brown trout during low flow periods are currently missing. Therefore, this hypothesis needs to be tested in further studies.

A second potential for the improvement of streamflow conditions consists in the retention of critical floods during the spawning and incubation season of brown trout (October to March). According to the analysis, however, this potential needs to be assessed as low. Only a small fraction of critical floods can be retained regardless of the reservoir location (cf. Figure 19). Interestingly, the data shows multiple critical flood events in every year (cf. Table A 5 in Appendix E). Still, brown trout populations have persisted in the Alp section for several years or decades (J.K. personal communication 14.03.2020). As the brown trout *Salmo trutta fario* is a territorial fish (Jonsson & Jonsson, 2011), a constant upstream migration of juveniles from several kilometers downstream of the Alp is unlikely. Hence, the high frequency of critical floods may indicate an underestimation of the critical flood intensity. A report from the canton of Schwyz (AquaPlus, 2009) states an exceedance of the critical flood level in the Alp downstream of Einsiedeln in 66% of the years (period 1997-2009), which supports this assumption.

Nevertheless, the capacity of the reservoir for retaining critical floods is not likely to change for higher (or lower) thresholds. The main reason is that the reservoir may only retain the fraction of the flood which is contributed by the Lümpebach (resp. 40% of this fraction in Brüschrain and 80% in Nätschberg). The area-based contribution of the Lümpebach to the Alp, however, is only about 10% in Brunni and 5% in Alpthal. Hence, the retention of a critical flood event may only succeed if the respective flood intensity in Brunni and/or Alpthal exceeds the threshold by less than 10% in Brunni and/or less than 5% in Alpthal.

5.3 Contribution to snowmaking

In the past 10 years, the natural snow cover has exceeded a compacted ski slope depth of 40 cm at Christmas in 4 out of 10 winters (cf. Figure 22). Hence, snowmaking was of significant importance for the ski resort Brunni-Haggenegg during at least 6 years. The analysis has shown that in 12 of the past 16 years (=75%), the snowmaking capacity (for the snow gun inventory of Brunni-Haggenegg) in December has been more than double as high as the required snow volume for the preparation of all three slopes (cf. Figure 20). This indicates that in most of the past winters not the meteorological conditions, but water access (i.e. reservoir size) would have been limiting to snowmaking before Christmas. Consequently, a reservoir with an adequate size has a remarkable potential to improve snow availability under present climate conditions.

Following the analysis, a water volume of 15'000 m³ is necessary to provide an adequate snow cover before Christmas. The applied safety factors of 1 resp. 1.5 ensure a slope cover with a compacted snow depth of 60 cm if no melting occurs (cf. section 3.4.3). These safety factors are important because no melting processes could be considered, since in most years the modelled natural snow depth is zero for at least some days in December (cf. Figure 22). For this reason, snowmaking was limited to the month of December, because a longer period would include a higher uncertainty with respect to melting processes.

Furthermore, snowmaking in November would influence water availability in December, because reservoir filling often takes several weeks in winter (cf. Figure 27). If reservoir storage is limited to 15'000 m³, early water abstraction for snowmaking may be problematic in winters with high snowmelt at the end of November/beginning of December and high snowmaking capacities shortly before Christmas holidays. In fact, the ski resort reported very high temperatures in December 2015 and 2016, where a promising natural snow cover in November melted completely within 1-2 weeks (Skilifte Brunni-Haggenegg AG, 2016, 2017), which is also visible in the natural snow cover simulation (cf. Figure 22). Consequently, in order to limit the risk of relevant water shortages shortly before Christmas, it is suggested to start snowmaking not before December if the reservoir storage is limited to 15'000 m³.

In January and February, natural snow cover increased to more than 20 cm in most winters and only moderate melting processes (< 20 cm in snow depth) can be observed (cf. Figure 22). Hence, water demand for snowmaking is assumed to be low if an adequate ski slope preparation is provided before Christmas. This conclusion is consistent with the information given by Keller et al. (2004), who report intensive snow production only until January for the study area.

Within this thesis, the effect of additional water abstraction from the Fischerebach on snowmaking has been neglected, because the goal of a multi-purpose reservoir would be to replace water abstraction from the Fischerebach completely. This can be justified by the relatively high area-based contribution of the Fischerebach to the streamflow in Brunni of around 30%. Thus, an adverse effect on downstream ecology by contemporary water abstraction cannot be

excluded. As an example, low streamflow increases the risk of spawning spots of brown trout to dry out (Crisp, 1996). Consequently, a reservoir might reduce potential stress for organisms suffering from current water abstraction for snowmaking. Further studies including field measurements in the Fischerebach and Alp are required to support this hypothesis.

Regarding the future snowmaking capacity, the results vary substantially depending on the simulation and on the assumed hours per day in which snowmaking is possible (cf. Figure 21). Still, the results show a distinct decline compared to the snowmaking capacity of the past years (cf. Figure A 19 in Appendix E). As the simulation data for the calculation of the wet-bulb temperature was limited to a daily resolution, the future snowmaking capacity was calculated for a snow gun operation of 12, 18 and 24 hours. In general, the DMI simulation is more optimistic than the SMHI simulation for future snowmaking conditions. For instance, with the 24h assumption the snowmaking capacity reaches the snow volume required for all slopes in 30% of the seasons in the SMHI simulation and in 60% in the DMI simulation. In both simulations, however, the difference between the results of the 12h and 24h assumption is critical, since the snowmaking capacity of the 24h assumption often exceeds the threshold for the required snow volume, whereas the 12h assumption does not (cf. Figure 21). This is not the case for the analogous calculation of the snowmaking capacity of past years, since anytime the results of the 24h assumption reach the threshold, this is also valid for the 12h assumption (cf. Figure A 19 in Appendix E).

Therefore, it is necessary to discuss whether the 12h, 18h or 24h assumption is best to predict future snowmaking capacity in order to evaluate the snowmaking potential of future years. As the snowmaking capacity increases non-linearly with lower wet-bulb temperatures (cf. Figure 14), the temporal evolution of the wet-bulb temperature below $-3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ throughout the day is very important. Hence, the use of daily averages in the calculation is problematic, as the evolution of the wet-bulb temperature throughout the day is unknown. Still, an indication for the best assumption can be provided by comparing the past snowmaking capacity based on hourly wet-bulb temperatures with the one based on daily wet-bulb temperatures (cf. Figure 20 and Figure A 19 in Appendix E). Interestingly, the 24h assumption is the best prediction showing the smallest deviations to the hourly resolution. Thus, following the results, a reservoir still shows a potential to benefit snowmaking in 30-60% of the seasons before Christmas in the near future.

Nevertheless, the results need to be considered with caution, because they focus only on the snowmaking capacity. Thus, effects of potential increases in melting processes or decreases in snowfall below 2000 m a.s.l. due to higher winter temperatures are not addressed (projected increase of $3.1\text{-}5.4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ by the end of the century in the RCP8.5 scenario) (CH2018, 2018). In fact, studies project a significant decrease in snow cover below 1500 m a.s.l. by mid-century (Schmucki et al., 2015; Steger et al., 2013) equivalent to an elevation shift of about 800 m by the end of the century (Bavay et al., 2013; Marty et al., 2017) in Switzerland. Hence, the demand for technical snow is likely to increase, whereas snowmaking at elevations below 1500 m a.s.l. will become more and more critical (Rixen et al., 2011; Steiger & Mayer, 2008).

5.4 Evaluation of trade-offs and proposal of prioritizations

5.4.1 Prioritization of intermittent purposes over streamflow augmentation

Concerning the trade-off between snowmaking and augmentation of streamflow for brown trout, it can be stated that the trade-off does not have the same implication for both purposes. Simultaneous water release for brown trout resulted in a missing water volume of more than 6'000 m³ for snowmaking in 2011 (cf. Table 9). This is equivalent to a snow volume deficit of around 50% for the preparation of all ski slopes. The consequence of this trade-off is a limited or even absent operation of the ski resort over Christmas holidays. Hence, even if snowmaking is possible in January, the deficit in revenue over Christmas is not likely to be compensated as described in various reports of the ski resort (Skilifte Brunni-Haggenegg AG, 2015, 2016, 2017). By contrast, the effect on brown trout consists of a total of 5 days (MFR 150 l/s in Alpthal, reservoir size of 15'000 m³, cf. Figure 26) on which streamflow cannot be augmented in December because of snowmaking. Thus, the impact on brown trout may be regarded as minor. Moreover, snowmaking in December does not affect streamflow augmentation for brown trout in January or February (not shown). As a conclusion, we suggest prioritizing snowmaking in December up to a water volume of 15'000 m³. Similarly, the augmentation of low streamflow in November should be limited in order to ensure a reservoir storage of 15'000 m³ for snowmaking at the beginning of December (cf. Figure 27).

The trade-off between tourism and augmentation of low streamflow is discussed in the following. It consists of a reduced potential for streamflow augmentation, because 80% of the reservoir storage is unavailable for water allocation in July (including some weeks in June if reservoir filling is necessary, cf. Figure 28). Interestingly, the overall effect on the augmentation of low streamflow of the months of July and August is limited to few days despite a maximum water allocation to brown trout of 20% in July (cf. Table 10). The reason for this is that in most years, 20% of the reservoir storage is sufficient to augment streamflow because streamflow only drops below the MFR on few single days. In summers with long periods of low streamflow (e.g. 2015 and 2018), however, the reduction in number of days in July is limited considerably compared to the single-purpose reservoir scenario (cf. Figure 29). This negative effect, however, is almost fully compensated in August, as 80% of the reservoir storage becomes available for water allocation. In the single-purpose scenario, this water volume is released in July resulting in an empty storage in August. Hence, we suggest keeping reservoir storage at least at 80% in July in order to boost summer tourism and focus on the augmentation of low flow in successive months.

5.4.2 Minimizing trade-offs of artificial flood experiments

The reservoir shows a great potential to conduct artificial flood experiments. A 300-year flood may be sustained for nearly 1 hour with a reservoir storage of 15'000 m³ and the largest flood ever recorded could be simulated with a reservoir storage of 30'000 m³ (cf. Figure 24 and Table 8). However, these results refer to a theoretical potential of the reservoir, as no assumptions

regarding construction aspects such as the diameter of the reservoir's outflow channel have been made. Moreover, potential effects of extreme flood experiments on the Lümpebach channel have been neglected and would need to be taken into account.

During an artificial flood experiment the reservoir storage is emptied or decreases substantially, which may have negative effects on different purposes on successive days or weeks. First, the impact on the augmentation of low streamflow is considered. In spring, the trade-off is limited to few days in May on which streamflow cannot be augmented due to previous water release of an artificial flood experiment. Moreover, this trade-off can be limited to almost zero if the remaining storage after a flood event is around 5'000 m³ (cf. Figure 30). This can be explained by the fact that in spring streamflow is almost always above the MFR, which is linked to the streamflow regime influenced by snowmelt in pre-alpine areas (Gustafsson et al., 2004; Keller et al., 2004). Therefore, we conclude that experiments with water volumes below 30'000 m³ at the beginning of April and May are possible (regardless of the reservoir location) without exerting a major negative effect on the augmentation of low streamflow for brown trout in present conditions.

A hidden trade-off not depicted in the overview of the time dependency of benefits (cf. Table 6) is the effect of extreme flood events on brown trout offspring in April. As the incubation phase ends in March (AquaPlus, 2009), the spawn is not likely to be destroyed by high streamflow in April. Still, the alevin dwell in the gravel bed for another month (Crisp, 2000; Jonsson & Jonsson, 2011) (cf. Appendix C). Thus, critical flood intensities may still exert some adverse effects. In fact, Nicola et al. (2009) reported a negative correlation between survival rate for both frequency and duration of high flow events, as alevin may be displaced to downstream areas with nonoptimal habitats. Therefore, the potential effect of artificial flood experiments on survival of brown trout offspring would need to be investigated further. A possible adaptation measure could be to generate floods in April only if the critical flood level has been exceeded several times in winter so that the potential loss of brown trout offspring is smaller. In other years, artificial flood experiments may be limited to the month of May.

In September, the trade-off with streamflow augmentation after the flood experiment is negligible for the studied period (cf. Figure 30). Before the experiment, however, water release needs to be limited in order to provide an adequate water volume for the artificial flood. In dry summers (e.g. 2015, 2018), the negative effects of tourism on augmentation of low streamflow are almost completely compensated in August. However, if water release needs to be limited in August due to artificial flood experiments starting in September, the negative effects cannot be compensated, and the trade-off can be considered problematic. Therefore, the additional benefit of a third artificial flood experiment is considered lower than the benefit for brown trout. Hence, it is generally not recommended to conduct artificial flood experiments in September. Still, in summers with high streamflow when stress levels in brown trout are considered to be low, an additional experiment in September can be conducted. In addition, only the effect of large flood events ($\geq 15'000$ m³) was analyzed. Possibly, already moderate water volumes

(< 5'000 m³) may be useful for certain research purposes. For such experiments, the trade-offs are likely to be much smaller, especially for larger reservoir sizes (e.g., 30'000 m³).

Artificial flood experiments may have a negative impact on tourism in April and July if reservoir storage is not refilled by 80% after the flood experiment. If the experiments are conducted at the beginning of May, the reservoir storage reached 80% in all analyzed years before the beginning of July (cf. Figure 25). Hence, there is no trade-off to be expected. If an artificial flood experiment is conducted at the beginning of April, however, there may be a potential trade-off during spring holidays. As the refilling time for water volumes of 15'000 m³ is restricted to less than 12 days in most years, this trade-off can be circumvented by not releasing larger water amounts.

Importantly, current climate scenarios for Switzerland project spring streamflow in pre-alpine areas to decline because of a decrease in snow cover and earlier snowmelt (FOEN, 2012; Marty et al., 2017). This hydrological trend has been observed in the study area for late spring; long time series show a significant decline of streamflow in May (Stähli et al., n.d., in review). Hence, potential trade-offs between artificial flood experiments and tourism may not be excluded in the future since lower streamflow increases the time for reservoir filling. Furthermore, the water demand for the augmentation of low streamflow for brown trout may increase in spring, as streamflow may drop below the minimum flow requirement more frequently in the future. Hence, the trade-off between artificial flood experiments and augmentation of low streamflow might increase. Therefore, the proposed management strategies are valid for contemporary conditions but may need to be adjusted in the future.

5.5 Suggestion for reservoir design and management

The following paragraphs consider the previously discussed aspects and conclusions in order to suggest an adequate reservoir design (i.e. volume and location) as well as a management strategy which mitigates trade-offs by a prioritization of purposes.

Regarding reservoir size, a reservoir volume between 20'000 m³ and 30'000 m³ is proposed, which is explained as follows. In order to take advantage of the potential for contemporary and future snowmaking, a reservoir storage of 15'000 m³ is required. As trade-offs can often be reduced with increasing reservoir size, a larger reservoir is beneficial. The potential for the retention of critical floods is completely realized with a reservoir size of 30'000 m³ (cf. Table 7). Furthermore, the simulation of historical flood events at the Lümpenenbach do not require larger water volumes (cf. Table 8). In addition, the number of days required for reservoir filling shows a striking difference between reservoir volumes of 30'000 m³ and 50'000 m³ in all analyzed months, especially at Bürschrain (cf. Figure 25 and Figure 28). Reservoir sizes larger than 30'000 m³ only show an additional benefit for the augmentation of low streamflow for brown trout. As the minimum flow requirement has been calculated using a statistical approach, the results are not as reliable as to justify the construction of a larger reservoir only for this purpose.

6. Conclusion

The presented work has developed a methodology for the assessment of the potential of small multi-purpose reservoirs in pre-alpine areas and applied it to a hypothetical reservoir in the Alptal. The developed methodology proposes two different scales of analysis, a macro-scale to determine possible reservoir purposes and a micro-scale to consider specific topographic factors for the selection of potential reservoir locations. Water abstraction to and water release from the reservoir was simulated by downscaling measured streamflow data area-based. Although the two analyzed reservoir locations Brüschrain and Nätschberg show distinct area-based water availabilities for abstraction, the results show a similar potential for both locations.

Regarding the improvement of streamflow conditions for brown trout (*Salmo trutta fario*) in the Alp, it has been shown that the reservoir's capacity to reduce floods (which may affect survival rate of brown trout offspring negatively) is very low. Regarding streamflow augmentation, however, already small reservoirs ($< 15'000 \text{ m}^3$) can reduce the number of days with low streamflow considerably. Still, even larger reservoirs ($100'000 \text{ m}^3$) are limited in augmenting streamflow during long periods of low flow. Hence, an intermittent augmentation may be considered to reduce potential stress for brown trout. Although further studies about the benefit of intermittent streamflow augmentation are required, the potential of the reservoir to reduce stress for brown trout (and possibly other riverine organisms) may be promising during low flow periods.

Regarding the potential for snowmaking, the provision of water is especially important before Christmas, as natural snow depth is usually increasing in the study area from January onwards. Under current climate conditions, a water volume of $15'000 \text{ m}^3$ is necessary for an adequate preparation of the ski slopes at Brunni-Haggenegg before Christmas. The snowmaking capacity exceeded the required snow volume in 13 of the past 16 winters. Therefore, the potential for snowmaking under current climate conditions is high if reservoir storage is at least $15'000 \text{ m}^3$ at the beginning of December. With respect to future meteorological conditions, the projected climate scenarios (RCP8.5) indicate a remarkable decrease in snowmaking capacity in the near future (2021-2050). Depending on the simulation model, the snowmaking potential in December will exceed the required snow volume in only 30-60% of the seasons. Hence, the meteorological conditions are likely to become limiting to snowmaking more often than reservoir storage.

In terms of reservoir design, a reservoir size between $20'000 \text{ m}^3$ and $30'000 \text{ m}^3$ is suggested. A reservoir volume within this range can reduce some of the trade-off between snowmaking and streamflow augmentation for brown trout in winter but also allows the simulation of an entire extreme event recorded at the Lümpebach station in an artificial flood experiment.

Furthermore, this volume can usually be refilled within 2-3 weeks (Nätschberg reservoir) resp. 2-6 weeks (Brüschrain reservoir) in most months.

Concerning management strategies, the evaluation of trade-offs has allowed the formulation of adequate prioritization rules for different purposes throughout the year. Artificial flood experiments are in focus in April and May because of the fast filling rate in spring months. In July, water release from the reservoir is proposed to be limited to 20% to provide a touristic benefit. This prioritization can be justified since the negative impact on streamflow augmentation in July is compensated in August, when 80% of the reservoir storage becomes available for water allocation. From August to November, water demand is mainly restricted to streamflow augmentation. In November and December, snowmaking is prioritized because the trade-off between snowmaking and streamflow augmentation shows larger effects on snowmaking than on brown trout.

In conclusion, this Master's thesis has shown that the elaboration of adequate management rules of a multi-purpose reservoir is possible without involving complex optimization models. Instead, management rules can be determined heuristically in a simple simulation model. The comparison between simulations of a single-purpose reservoir and a multi-purpose reservoir allows the detection and assessment of trade-offs between different water uses. As multi-purpose reservoirs are currently discussed as an adaptation measure to mitigate effects of climate change in Switzerland, the evaluation of the multi-purpose potential could be interesting especially in areas where small reservoirs already exist. Thus, the proposed methodology may be applied to any small reservoir in order to evaluate its multi-purpose potential. In terms of ecological benefits of small reservoirs, which was intended to be illustrated with streamflow augmentation for brown trout, however, there are still many research gaps. More comprehensive studies could provide more transparency on how small reservoirs could be managed to include ecological benefits, which might change the rather negative perception of artificial reservoirs from an ecological perspective in the future.

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Appendix

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A – Hydrology of the Lümpenenbach (incl. reservoir design) and Alp

Figure A 1: Discharge variability of the Lümpenenbach catchment. A) interannual discharge variability (period 1990-2019), B) daily discharge variability of the year 2016.

Figure A 2: Calculation of the design volume V_d of a reservoir by Hänggi und Weingartner (2012). Q_{min} = Minimum discharge, Q_d = Design discharge, Q_{max} = Maximum discharge (i.e. maximum discharge the reservoir can withdraw).

Figure A 3: Flow duration curve of the Lümpenenbach considering three different periods (1979-1999, 1989-2009 and 1999-2019).

Figure A 4: Reservoir zones in WEAP. Flood control zone: Vacant/only accessed during floods. Conservation and buffer zone: Active storage. Buffer zone: Water release limited by a buffer coefficient. Inactive zone: Water not available for allocation. (SEI, 2020)

Source: www.weap21.org/WebHelp/reservoir_zones.htm

Figure A 5: Natural hazard map concerning floods of the Lümpenenbach catchment. Yellow: Low risk. Blue: Intermediate risk. Red: High risk. Brown: No classification.

Table A 1: Statistical values of Q329 and Q310 (l/s) of the Alp in Einsiedeln for the period 1992-2018.

Streamflow [l/s]	Q329	Q310
Minimum	282	302
Median	442	507
Maximum	798	919

Table A 2: Statistical values of seasonal MN3Q of the Alp in Einsiedeln for the period 1992-2018.

MN3Q [l/s]	Winter (DJF)	Spring (MAM)	Summer (JJA)	Autumn (SON)
Minimum	181	263	163	149
25% Quantile	333	498	321	290
Median	421	602	429	387
75% Quantile	516	851	528	475
Maximum	726	1099	737	685

Table A 3: Statistical values of seasonal MN7Q of the Alp in Einsiedeln for the period 1992-2018.

MN7Q [l/s]	Winter (DJF)	Spring (MAM)	Summer (JJA)	Autumn (SON)
Minimum	194	289	169	183
25% Quantile	385	540	412	306
Median	465	630	495	416
75% Quantile	575	983	604	527
Maximum	752	1608	911	772

Table A 4: Fishing statistics of the Alp (section Brunni-Einsiedeln). Source: www.isfv.ch

	Brown trout (<i>Salmo trutta fario</i>)	Rainbow trout (<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>)	Brook trout (<i>Salvelinus fontinalis</i>)	Grayling (<i>Thymallus thymallus</i>)
2016	245	1	0	0
2017	417	0	0	0
2018	350	0	0	0
2019	398	0	0	0

B – Field measurements

Figure A 6: Channel width measured at the first sill downstream of the field measurement point in Brunni. Picture taken on the 29.08.2020, 11:00 am.

Figure A 7: Channel width measured at the sill directly south of the field measurement point in Alpthal. Picture taken on the 22.07.2020, 4:00 pm.

Figure A 8: Cumulative precipitation at the Lümpenenbach before and during the discharge measurements (marked in yellow).

Figure A 9: Cumulative precipitation and measured streamflow at the Lümpenenbach streamflow gauge before and after the discharge measurements (marked in yellow) on the 29.08.2020.

Figure A 10: Visible differences in discharge of the Alp in Alpthal on the 29.08.2020. Left: 11:00 am, right: 06:30 pm.

C – General information on the brown trout *Salmo trutta fario*

The brown trout *Salmo trutta fario* is a predatory fish living in cold (average temperatures < 20 °C in summer), fast flowing and oxygen-rich waters. Furthermore, they require clean water with pH values close to neutral as well as riverbeds with coarse gravel or pebbles for reproduction (Baglinière & Maisse, 1999). The capacity of brown trout to tolerate anthropogenic interventions (e.g. change in structure, water temperature, flow or chemical components) is low, therefore it is used as an indicator species for the assessment of the status of rivers (FOEN, 2004). Moreover, it is the characteristic fish species for the identification of the trout zone, representing the uppermost zone of a river, characterized by fast flowing water, cold temperatures and low turbidity during baseflow (LfU Baden-Württemberg, 2005).

By origin, the brown trout is a European species, as it distributed from northern Europe over the entire continent before being spread by humans on a global scale (Jonsson & Jonsson, 2011). In terms of taxonomy, *Salmo trutta fario* is considered a morph of the brown trout species *Salmo trutta*, which forms part of the family Salmonidae. Other morphological adaptations of the species include *Salmo trutta trutta* (the sea trout) and *Salmo trutta lacustris* (the lake trout), referring to their trophic habitats (Jonsson & Jonsson, 2011).

Figure A 11: The brown trout *Salmo trutta fario*. Source: iowadnr.gov

The life cycle of the brown trout is depicted in Figure A 12. Mature females spawn during autumn or early winter in gravel beds (Crisp, 1996), in the Alp spawning takes place from middle of October to end of November (AquaPlus, 2009). Preferred spawning sites are at the transition zone when pools merge into riffles (Fleming, 1996; Louhi et al., 2008; Stuart, 1953). In this zone, water current accelerates due to decreasing water depth, resulting in low concentrations of fine sediment or sand in gravel beds (Fleming, 1996). Hence, permeability is relatively high, which affects intragravel dissolved oxygen concentration and thus embryo survival positively (Chapman, 1988; Fleming, 1996). The eggs are deposited in gravel at a water depth of about 10-65 cm (Crisp, 1996; Jonsson & Jonsson, 2011; Louhi et al., 2008), in the Alp at a depth of

about 10-25 cm (AquaPlus, 2009). The duration of the incubation time is highly depending on water temperature (Crisp, 2000; Jonsson & Jonsson, 2011), in the Alp fertilized eggs hatch towards the end of March (AquaPlus, 2009). The so-called “alevin” dwell for about a month in the gravel bed feeding on the remaining yolk before emerging from the gravel, filling their swim bladder with air and attaining neutral buoyance. At this stage, the young fish is called “fry” and starts feeding on external food (Crisp, 2000; Jonsson & Jonsson, 2011). At the time the fry begins to establish and defend its territory, it is named “parr”. In comparison to other salmonid species, *Salmo trutta fario* do not migrate and leave their territory only for reproduction or during disturbances (Crisp, 2000). They attain maturity at different ages, between 1 to 5 years depending on various factors such as growth rate and temperature (Jonsson & Jonsson, 2011).

Figure A 12: Life cycle of the brown trout (*Salmo trutta fario*).

The habitat use of brown trout depends on their size and age. Small and young individuals usually exploit shallow areas at water depths between 5 and 30 cm (Jonsson & Jonsson, 2011). With increasing fish size, they move to deeper and faster stream habitats. Figure A 13 shows the water depth and velocity preferences of brown trout based on the habitat suitability index established by Heggenes (1996). They favour intermediate depths with an optimum between 40 and 80 cm. Adult individuals tend to be found in depressions of the channel bed or below overhanging and underwashed banks with local swirls (Jonsson & Jonsson, 2011). They avoid stillwater as well as high water velocities, whereas micro-areas with snout velocities (i.e. the velocity the fish experiences) less than 20 cm/s are selected for (Heggenes, 1996). Crisp (1996) indicates velocities between 20 and 30 cm/s to be optimal. Snout velocities can be adjusted by moving up or down in the water column. In terms of temperature, the optimum ranges between 4 and 19 °C, meaning that temperatures below and above this range induce stress (Elliott,

1981). Elliott (1994) stated water temperature to be a key variable as low temperatures inhibit growth, whereas warm temperatures increase mortality.

Figure A 13: Habitat suitability index for habitat use by brown trout with respect to a) total water depth and b) mean water velocity. Source: Heggenes (1996).

D – Determination of critical low water level and associated streamflow

In practice, there are various methods for the determination of a minimum discharge which take fish migration into account. Dönni et al. (2016) lists three methods that are commonly used in Switzerland:

1) Water release experiments

In the field, water depth is measured along cross-sections and longitudinal profiles of the river on several days with different streamflow values. Thus, information of the water depth at different spots during different discharge conditions is gained, which allows the identification of critical spots as well as an approximation of critical streamflow quantities. This method, however, is only recommended if discharge values can be kept constant during the measurements, i.e. the reservoir needs to be located on or next to the river. Moreover, the detection of all critical spots is difficult since data points are discrete and thus the river morphology is not covered entirely.

2) Numerical-hydraulic 2d model

During low water levels, a survey of the riverbed is conducted by using land-based (theodolite) or airborne techniques (LIDAR) in order to generate a digital terrain model. Based on the data, a 2d-Modell is created enabling the calculation of water depths, flow velocities and flow directions for any discharge quantity at any point in the riverbed. Additional cross-section and discharge measurements at critical points within the riverbed can be used for model calibration. However, this method is time-consuming, and the survey equipment and modelling software is costly.

3) Field measurements during low water flow

Water depth is measured along cross-sections and longitudinal profiles during several days of low streamflow. Compared to the first method, the reservoir installation is not yet constructed, so the consistency of discharge values is not guaranteed. Furthermore, the feasibility of the measurements is completely dependent on the local streamflow conditions, meaning they can only be executed if low flow periods occur.

Other methods mentioned by the agency for environmental protection of Baden-Württemberg LfU (2005) include:

4) Methods based on seasonal/monthly discharge statistics

One commonly applied method for the determination of a minimum discharge in the state of Baden-Württemberg includes the calculation of *MNQ*, which is the arithmetic mean of the lowest daily streamflow values of every year over a certain period of time. In general, minimum discharge is set to 1/3 of *MNQ*. This value serves as a first estimate and is tested for the ecological conditions of the respective river.

This includes

- a. the determination of ecological criteria such as the identification of indicator species and their ecological requirements
- b. selecting representative spots (cross-sections) within the riverbed the ecological criteria are tested for

As a result, the first estimate is adjusted to meet the ecological criteria in the representative spots. As ecological requirements for indicator species may differ throughout the year, the minimum discharge can vary accordingly. For instance, during the spawning and developing phase of the indicator fish species, minimum discharge can be adjusted to the *MNQ* of the respective season or month. Hence, natural variation in discharge is taken into account.

5) Methods based on the catchment area

Other approaches determine the minimum discharge according to the size of the catchment area, the type of flow duration curve and special fish migration criteria such as the availability of fish ladders. For catchment areas smaller than 20 km², the estimate for the determination of the minimum discharge is 9/10 of *MNQ*.

E – Additional results

Improvement of streamflow conditions for brown trout

Figure A 14: Total number of days with streamflow values below the minimum flow requirement of a) 90 l/s, b) 110 l/s in Brunni. Shown is the period 2009-2019 (11 years). The number of days is evaluated for different reservoir sizes (x-axis) and the two reservoir locations Brüschrain (yellow) and Nätschberg (blue).

Figure A 15: As Figure 15b but showing monthly resolution and only for Nätschberg. The bars represent absolute numbers for the period 2009-2019, colours represent different reservoir volumes (m³).

Figure A 16: Streamflow evolution of the Alp in Alpthal from June-December 2018 with and without reservoir (left y-axis) and corresponding evolution of the reservoir storage (right y-axis).

Figure A 17: Streamflow evolution of the Alp in Alpthal from October-December 2011 with and without reservoir (left y-axis) and corresponding evolution of the reservoir storage (right y-axis).

Figure A 18: Number of days with streamflow values above the critical flood level (CFR) of 2.09 m³/s in Alpthal during the period 2009-2019. Values are shown for the reference scenario (no reservoir) and for the reservoir locations Brüschrain and Nätschberg (unlimited reservoir size).

Table A 5: Number of days on which discharge exceeds the critical flood level (CFR) of 1.39 m³ in Brunni resp. 2.09 m³ in Alpthal in the reference scenario (no reservoir).

	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Q > CFL in Brunni	8	4	7	4	1	8	6	9	10	7
Q > CFL in Alpthal	12	7	8	7	2	9	7	9	12	9

Snowmaking

Figure A 19: Technical snowmaking capacity for the years 2004-2019 using meteorological data recorded at the Erlenbach station (daily resolution). Snowmaking capacity calculated for a daily snow gun operation of 12, 18 and 24 hours.

Figure A 20: Unmet water demand for snowmaking considering different reservoir sizes at the Brüschrain location.

Artificial flood experiments

Figure A 21: Return periods of different streamflow intensities of the Lümpenbach (red line) with 95% confidence interval (blue lines). Black dots represent yearly maxima recorded at the Lümpenbach station. Applied method: Maximum likelihood estimates. Data: Streamflow values recorded at the Lümpenbach streamflow gauges (10 min resolution) from 1985-2019.

Figure A 22: Discharge hydrograph for yearly flood events of selected years.

Trade-offs

Figure A 23: Trade-off between snowmaking and augmentation of low streamflow for brown trout from the perspective of brown trout. Shown is the number of days with discharge values below 200 l/s in Alpthal (period 2009-2019, winter season) with a single purpose reservoir (brown trout only) and a multi-purpose reservoir (brown trout and snowmaking). Reservoir location: Nättschberg.

Table A 6: Trade-off between snowmaking and streamflow augmentation (MFR of 110 l/s in Brunni and 200 l/s in Alpthal) for brown trout from the perspective of snowmaking. Trade-off expressed as missing water volume [m³] for snowmaking for different reservoir volumes at Nättschberg. Non-displayed years from 2009-2019 do not show missing water volumes (no trade-off).

Year \ Vol. Res.	2011	2014	2016
15'000 m³	1'878	4'427	3'887
30'000 m³	1'878	231	1'588
50'000 m³	1'878	0	1'263

Figure A 24: Number of days with streamflow values below 200 l/s in Alpthal during the period 2009-2019 for a single-purpose reservoir (brown trout only) and for a multi-purpose reservoir (brown trout and tourism) located at Nätschberg.

Table A 7: Trade-off between tourism and augmentation of low streamflow for brown trout (BT). Shown is the number of days with streamflow values below 200 l/s in Alpthal for a single-purpose reservoir (BT only) and multi-purpose reservoir (BT and tourism) located at Nätschberg during the months of July and August (period 2009-2019).

Reservoir size	BT only July + August	BT & tourism July + August	Trade-off
15'000 m ³	105	114	9
30'000 m ³	97	107	10
50'000 m ³	92	102	10

Figure A 25: Trade-off between artificial flood experiments (AFE) and augmentation of low streamflow for brown trout (BT) from the perspective of brown trout. Shown is the number of days with discharge values below 200 l/s in Alpthal (period 2009-2019, months May and September) in a single purpose reservoir system (BT only) and multi-purpose reservoir system (BT and AFE). Number in brackets show the remaining reservoir storage after an artificial flood experiment. Reservoir location: Nätschberg.